

Policy Cloud
Cloud for Data-Driven Policy Management

CLOUD FOR DATA-DRIVEN POLICY MANAGEMENT

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Abstract: This series of deliverables will describe the dissemination and collaboration strategy and the activities followed during the reporting periods as well as the results from these activities. This is the updated Communication and Dissemination Strategy of M24, and an updated version will be delivered in M36.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation/Acronym	Definition
BDVA	Big Data Value Association
CERIF	Common European Research Information Format
CRS	Common Reporting Standard
EBDVF	European Big Data Value Forum
EC	European Commission
EC DGA	European Commission - Data Governance Act
ECSA	European Citizen Science Association
EUOS	European Observatory for ICT Standardisation
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC DIH	European Open Science Cloud Digital Innovation Hub
GA	Grant Agreement
MAG	Gruppo Maggioli
H2020	Horizon 2020
ICT	Information Communication Technology
ICTLC	ICT Legal Consulting
ICB	Impact Creation Board
ICCS	Institute of Communication and Computers System
IEEE	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
OASC	Open & Agile Smart Cities
OS	Open Source
OSS	Open-Source Software
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud
SME	Small-Medium Enterprise
SDO	Standards Developing Organisation
TF	Task Force
TWG	Technical Working Group
WP	Work Package

Contents

Versioning and Contribution History.....	2
Author List.....	2
Abbreviations and Acronyms	3
Executive Summary.....	10
1 Introduction	12
1.1 Communications Overview	12
1.2 Stakeholder analysis.....	15
1.3 Summary of changes.....	16
2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy Key Pillars	17
2.1 Policy Cloud Services	17
2.2 Pilot Use Cases.....	18
2.3 Exploitable Results	19
3 Onboarding End-users	20
3.1 Onboarding end-users at national level.....	20
3.1.1 Onboard in activities Year 1.....	20
3.1.2 Onboarding activities Year 2	21
3.1.3 Future steps	22
3.2 Linking pilot policy challenges to EU policy making.....	22
3.2.1 Onboarding activities Year 1	24
3.2.2 Onboarding activities Year 2	25
3.2.3 Future steps	27
3.3 Policy Cloud in the context of EOSC European Open Science Cloud	28
3.3.1 Onboarding activities Year 1	28
3.3.2 Onboarding activities Year 2	29
3.3.3 Future steps	30
3.4 Impact Creation Board.....	30
3.4.1 Onboarding activities Year 1	31
3.4.2 Onboarding activities Year 2	31
3.4.3 Future steps	32
3.5 Synergies	33

3.5.1	Onboarding activities Year 1	33
3.5.2	Onboarding activities Year 2	35
3.5.3	Future steps	40
4	Communications and Dissemination Plan	41
4.1	Visual Identity & Branding	41
4.1.1	Branding activities Year 1	42
4.1.2	Branding activities Year 2	43
4.1.3	Next steps	45
4.2	Policy Cloud Website	45
4.2.1	Website activities Year 1	45
4.2.2	Website activities Year 2	47
4.2.3	Next steps	49
4.3	Social Media Channels	49
4.3.1	Social Media activities Year 1	50
4.3.2	Social Media activities Year 2	52
4.3.3	Next steps	52
4.4	Newsletters	53
4.4.1	Newsletter activities Year 1	53
4.4.2	Newsletter activities Year 2	53
4.4.3	Next steps	54
4.5	Videos	54
4.5.1	Social Media activities Year 1	55
4.5.2	Video activities Year 2	55
4.5.1	Next steps	56
4.6	Communications Toolkit	57
4.6.1	Communication Toolkit Year 1	57
4.6.2	Communication Toolkit Year 2	59
4.6.3	Next steps	61
4.7	Publications	61
4.7.1	Publication activities Year 1	61
4.7.2	Publication activities Year 2	62
4.7.3	Future steps	64

5	Policy Cloud workshops, webinars, third party events and podcasts	66
5.1	COVID-19	66
5.1.1	Mitigation Actions Year 1	66
5.1.2	Mitigation Actions Year 2	67
5.1.3	Future steps	68
5.2	Policy Cloud workshops	68
5.2.1	Policy Cloud activities Year 1	68
5.2.2	Policy Cloud activities Year 2	68
5.2.3	Next steps.....	72
5.3	Policy Cloud webinars	72
5.3.1	Webinars Year 1	73
5.3.2	Webinars Year 2	73
5.3.3	Next steps.....	74
5.4	Pilot Co-creation workshops.....	74
5.4.1	Co-creation activities Year 1	74
5.4.2	Co-creation activities Year 2	75
5.4.3	Future steps	75
5.5	Podcasts	75
5.5.1	Podcasts Year 1	75
5.5.2	Podcasts Year 2	76
5.5.3	Next steps.....	77
5.6	Third Party Events	77
5.6.1	Third Party Events Year 1	78
5.6.2	Third Party Events Year 2	79
5.6.3	Next steps.....	80
6	Measuring impact and monitoring activities	81
6.1	KPIs.....	81
6.2	Monitoring	87
6.3	Communications Timeline.....	89
7	Conclusions.....	90
	Bibliography.....	91
	ANNEX 1 - Policy Cloud Dissemination Channels and Mechanisms.....	94

List of Tables

Table 1: The three phases of Policy Cloud Communication and Dissemination Strategy	14
Table 2: Policy Cloud Stakeholder analysis and mapping.....	15
Table 3: Policy Cloud Exploitable Assets	19
Table 4: Policy Cloud Pilots added value linked to EC Policymaking.....	24
Table 5: Sample of strategic connections to multipliers on the Policy Cloud key pillars	52
Table 6: Scientific publications made by the Policy Cloud consortium.....	64
Table 7: Mitigation Mechanisms for COVID-19 challenges	67
Table 8: Mitigation mechanisms for COVID-19 challenges continued in year 2	68
Table 9: Webinar overview year 2	74
Table 10: Overview of third-party events attended by Policy Cloud at M12.....	78
Table 11: Overview of third-party events attended by Policy Cloud at M24.....	80
Table 12: KPI definition, monitoring and roadmap for M25-36.....	87

List of Figures

Figure 1 - Policy Cloud communication & dissemination channels and mechanisms.....	14
Figure 2: Overview Policy Cloud services.....	17
Figure 3: Policy Cloud pilot use cases: web page Impression	18
Figure 4: Who benefits flyers targeted at national end-users.....	20
Figure 5: Tweet by Major Cities in Europe, showcasing the Urbanpolicymaking in Sofia pilot in Policy Cloud	22
Figure 6: Policy Cloud pilots and collaborations linking local poliocymaking challenges to the EU policy contexts.	26
Figure 7: Overview of the impact of the Policy Cloud Data Driven Policy Week.	27
Figure 8: Policy Cloud services	29
Figure 9: Suzanne Dumouchel, EOSC Association Director and partner in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project, as speaker in the plenary session “From Digital Disruption to Digital Adoption”	30
Figure 10: Website banner presenting the first four Impact Creation Board members, linking to a dedicated Policy Cloud webpage.....	31
Figure 11: Michela Magas, Policy Cloud ICB member as speaker at the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021	32
Figure 12: sample of promotional banner Big Data Pilot Demo Days at BDV PPP 2020.....	33
Figure 13: Smart Society Parallel Session Smart Government with co-creating services using AI and Data	34
Figure 14: The Data Driven Policy Cluster Roadmap.....	36
Figure 15: Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021, Plenary Keynote speakers Day 1	37
Figure 16: Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021, Plenary Keynote speakers Day 2	37

Figure 17: Data Driven Policy Cluster @enabling Data Economy for local communities session (EBDVF2021).....	38
Figure 18: Webinar Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations announcement	39
Figure 19: Promotional banner Data Driven Policymaking for the food value chain	40
Figure 20: Brand manual defining use of logo and colour palette	41
Figure 21: Icons for Policy Cloud pilots	42
Figure 22: Icons designed for Policy Cloud services.....	42
Figure 23: Impressions of the Policy Cloud branded communication material.....	43
Figure 24: Sample of one of the three Policy Cloud Data Marketplace user journey infographics	44
Figure 25: Impressions of the home-page (left) and deliverables page (right) on the Policy Cloud website	46
Figure 26: Policy Cloud Website Dashboard	46
Figure 27: Scientific Publications page, all entries are filterable for type of publication.....	47
Figure 28: Press Clippings page	48
Figure 29: Sample of the Be Part of Policy Cloud page.....	49
Figure 30: Sample of branded, content rich social media posts	50
Figure 31: A major event being highlighted in a recent edition of the Policy Cloud newsletter.....	54
Figure 32: Policy Cloud YouTube channel	55
Figure 33: Policy Cloud YouTube playlist with 4 categories.....	56
Figure 34: Sample of the Policy Cloud demo graphic visualisation of Management of data from the Global Terrorism Data Base	57
Figure 35: Policy Cloud Communication Toolkit on the project website	58
Figure 36: sample of the Data Driven Policy Cluster branding	59
Figure 37: Virtual background with branding of the event and cluster	60
Figure 38: Sample of Policy Cloud branded sustainable cups, potential promotional material for the final project event.....	61
Figure 39: Sample of Policy Cloud webpage publications, posters and presentations	62
Figure 40: Policy Cloud Outreach submenu.....	62
Figure 41: Announcement of the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021	69
Figure 42: Stakeholder distribution for the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit registrants	70
Figure 43: Session banners of the policy focused day 1 at the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021	70
Figure 44: Session banners for tools and mechanisms focused day 2 of the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021	71
Figure 45: Overview of EGI 2021 session speakers, from the cluster and EOCS.....	72
Figure 46: promotional image of post-co-creation workshop report.....	75
Figure 47: Policy Cloud podcast on Policies against radicalisation Pilot.....	76
Figure 48: The four podcast episodes on the podcast hosting platform Anchor.fm	76
Figure 49: Slider on the homepage of the website promoting the podcast	77
Figure 50: Impression of the Policy Cloud monitoring Dashboard.....	88

Figure 51: sample timeline of communication activities M25-M3089
Figure 52: Policy Cloud Communication & Dissemination channels and mechanisms.....94

Executive Summary

Via four strategically designed pilot use cases to be coordinated in **Bulgaria, Italy, Spain and the United Kingdom**, Policy Cloud will deliver a unique, integrated environment of curated datasets and data manipulation and analysis tools of fundamental importance to stakeholders across Europe.

The aim of Policy Cloud is to harness the potential of digitisation, big data and cloud technologies to improve the modelling, creation and implementation of policies. From a communications perspective, this goal requires reaching and engaging a broad range of critical stakeholders including policy makers and the big data community through carefully planned communication and dissemination activities and rich, consistent and relevant content.

In October 2020, the EC approved its new Open-Source Software Strategy 2020-2023¹, a part of the overarching Digital Strategy of the Commission² and contributing to the Digital Europe programme. Policy Cloud will contribute to this strategy through its use and upstream contributions to open source.

Moreover, with the Data Governance Act of November 2020³ the European Commission proposed new rules on data governance. Their aim is to **exploit the high amounts of data created every day, but within a trustworthy European framework**. These new rules will allow European data to be harnessed and **allow specific European data spaces to benefit society, citizens and companies**. The Commission has proposed nine data spaces in February 2020's data strategy⁴, ranging from industry to energy, and from health to the European Green Deal. Policy Cloud is exactly the type of instrument which will be able to exploit these large quantities of data in order to benefit society, citizens, and companies, while protecting the data and ensuring GDPR standards are maintained.

This Communication and Dissemination Strategy is the second in a series of three deliverables. It details the specific communication and dissemination activities to be implemented, the innovation and policy landscape it is set in, the stakeholder groups to be targeted, and the tools to be used over the life of the project to support the achievement of project goals.

Section 1 enlarges on the project objectives and provides an overview of the communication activities that will support them. The stakeholder groups are also defined along with the benefits each will derive from the project. And includes a summary of changes for year 2.

¹ EC, EC adopts new software strategy https://ec.europa.eu/info/news/european-commission-adopts-new-open-source-software-strategy-2020-2023-2020-oct-20_en, retrieved 2020-12-21

² EC, European Digital Strategy <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/content/european-digital-strategy>, retrieved 2020-12-21

³ EC, European Data Governance Act, <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/news/proposal-regulation-european-data-governance-data-governance-act>, retrieved 2020-12-21

⁴ EC, European Data Strategy <https://ec.europa.eu/info/strategy/priorities-2019-2024/europe-fit-digital-age/european-data-strategy>, retrieved 2020-12-21

Section 2 presents the key pillars of the communication strategy, namely the Policy Cloud Services, the pilot use cases, and the key exploitable results.

Section 3 explores the relevance of the project within the broader European landscape particularly as regards prevailing digital policy, the creation of the EOCS, and EU funding priorities as evidenced by Horizon Europe.

Section 4 describes the communications tools and channels which will be used, both on and offline.

Section 5 describes the workshops, webinars, podcasts and other events planned for stakeholder engagement and end user onboarding. The reality of COVID-19 affecting these events is addressed in this section.

Section 6 presents the online dashboard and associated impact monitoring and measurement tools which will be used throughout the duration of the project.

Section 7 provides concluding remarks.

1 Introduction

Via four separate pilot use cases to be coordinated in Bulgaria, Italy, Spain and the United Kingdom, Policy Cloud will deliver a unique, integrated environment of curated datasets and data manipulation and analysis tools which will be made available to stakeholders across Europe.

As well as a tangible demonstration of the efficacy of the project itself, these pilot use cases, along with the toolkit of services to be developed during their evolution, will be the key source of the rich content which will support the dissemination strategy throughout the 36 months of the project.

The main objectives of this strategy are the following:

- Integrating the project into the global ecosystem of Big data driven policy development and management
- Federating Big data innovator communities for policy management
- Attracting public administrations, governments, think tanks and other policy making organisations
- Engaging with pilot use case stakeholders
- Disseminating technical results
- Reaching data providers and policy makers
- Supporting the project's commercialisation and market uptake strategy
- Organising marketing campaigns for the Data Marketplace.

1.1 Communications Overview

Using a content-driven approach, dissemination activities will be closely integrated with project activities. As such, they may be divided into three distinct phases:

1. **During the first 12 months** as the pilot use cases are set up (Phase 1) the focus was therefore on the foundation of communication activities such as planning, creating dissemination guidelines, identifying and analysing target audiences, and establishing a brand identity and associated marketing collateral.
2. **Between month 12 and month 24**, (Phase 2) the focus lay on documenting and showcasing the results of the pilot use cases. This will require the identification of exploitation targets and the dissemination of information both online and through trade and industry channels, scientific publications, and conference appearances.
3. **Between month 24 and 36** (Phase 3) the focus will be on encouraging adoption of the key project assets via exhibitions and trade fairs, live demonstrations and client presentations.

The table below shows the what, why and how of the three phases.

	Year 1: Communication & market awareness	Year 2: Case studies & dissemination	Year 3: Communication & market uptake
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning: Dissemination plan for R&I + industry • Dissemination guidelines: shared visions - what & how. • Identify and attract target audience • Define tailored messaging • Corporate design & branding • Engage with local ecosystems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 Case study results • Exploitation targets • Online dissemination: Press & media, guide • Scientific community: Publications & event presentations • Industrial community: Adoption, events, industry media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toolkit ready • Use case demos & training • High-profile conferences & events • Policy cloud foundation – sustainability & commercialisation • Scientific & industry dissemination
Why	Set up foundation for Y1 &2 and leverage results from state of the art (D2.1) & market analysis (D7.1)	Collect feedback & value proposition to ensure service adoption & sustainability for the long-term	Create interest & opportunities for service adoption by target stakeholders. Increase both commercial and scientific impact of project & exploitation opportunities
How	Identify stakeholders & engage with them using adequate communication tools & channels. Create communication pieces to spread the word & raise awareness	Demos of assets, define value propositions & engage with stakeholders through events, workshops & webinars trainings	Consolidation of synergies with EOSC & H2020 projects, EU bodies & stakeholders & leverage with industrial players
What	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning: Dissemination plan for R&I + industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 Case study results • Exploitation targets 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Toolkit ready

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Dissemination guidelines: shared visions - what & how. Identify and attract target audience Define tailored messaging Corporate design & branding Engage with local ecosystems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Online dissemination: Press & media, guide Scientific community: Publications & event presentations Industrial community: Adoption, events, industry media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Use case demos & training High-profile conferences & events Policy cloud foundation – sustainability & commercialisation Scientific & industry dissemination
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TABLE 1: THE THREE PHASES OF POLICY CLOUD COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY

The strategy will make use of a mix of channels and mechanisms to raise awareness of the Policy Cloud project results and activities and onboard end-users. These channels and mechanisms are illustrated in the infographic below, and in annex 1 for an enlarged version of the infographic.

FIGURE 1 - POLICY CLOUD COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION CHANNELS AND MECHANISMS

1.2 Stakeholder analysis

The table below identifies the key stakeholders in Policy Cloud and defines the main benefits expected to be derived by each group from the project.

Category	Stakeholder Groups	Benefits
Policy Makers & Public Administrations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC, national, regional policymakers • Municipalities • NGOs • SDOs 	<p>Improved efficiency and effectiveness of the policymaking process through access to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scenario simulations to model and evaluate policy impacts • Analytical tools to enhance the predictive power of data • Cleaned, refined, structured and trustworthy European datasets emerging from the pilot use cases
Research & Innovation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EC-funded projects • EOSC • Big data experts • Researchers in the human and social sciences • BDVA • Open-Source Communities 	<p>Better quality research outcomes through access to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solutions and policy making services available through EOSC • Previous project results upon which to build further
Industry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Big data providers • Cloud providers • Big data solutions providers 	<p>Improved efficiencies and new business opportunities through access to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Novel data management and analysis solutions • Tools for cleaning and refining data • The Data Marketplace as a shop window via which to offer new datasets
Citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Residents at pilot use case sites • Citizens impacted by future Policy Cloud adoptions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved quality of life through • Participation in policy making • Continuous improvement policy design • Creation of targeted policies

TABLE 2: POLICY CLOUD STAKEHOLDER ANALYSIS AND MAPPING

1.3 Summary of changes

Deliverable 7.13 is the M24 (December 2021) update of Deliverable 7.6, Communication and Dissemination Strategy⁵ where we are reporting on the communication and dissemination activities of M13-M24, took stock of the impact and analysed the strategy in place. Sections 3-5 reports on the activities performed in year 2 and defines the future steps based on the impact achieved and KPIs set for December 2022 (M36).

In addition, section 6 has an updated overview of the KPIs and a new timeline for M25-30.

⁵ Willems, Marieke, Muscella, Silvana, Biller, Tracey, & Smith, Zachary. (2020). D7.6 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION STRATEGY. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5106487>

2 Communication and Dissemination Strategy Key

Pillars

The pilot use cases, the suite of services to be developed during their evolution, and the exploitable results which emerge from the project are the key pillars of the Policy Cloud communication strategy. These three pillars are discussed in detail here.

2.1 Policy Cloud Services

Policy Cloud will provide an integrated suite of six services designed to facilitate the transformation of raw data into valuable and actionable knowledge to be used in efficient and effective policy creation. These services will be branded to Policy Cloud in the first instance but with a view ultimately to being incorporated into the EOSC Exchange or EOSC Core.

FIGURE 2: OVERVIEW POLICY CLOUD SERVICES

It is envisaged that the Policy Cloud Data marketplace will enable the creation of an entire ecosystem where all stakeholders may produce, contribute, process, and use policy-related data assets. Alongside the Data marketplace, the reusable models and tools are the foundation for the proposed dual-business plan which the consortium has formulated to ensure the long-term sustainability and take-up of the Policy Cloud results. The Marketplace software prototype was delivered in M20, in the third year WP7 will be working on dedicated promotional campaigns targeted at onboarding potential end users.

2.2 Pilot Use Cases

During the course of the Policy Cloud project, four separate pilot use cases are coordinated in Bulgaria, Italy, Spain and the United Kingdom.

As well as providing a framework for the tools, models and data which will populate the cloud, the pilot use cases are a **key source of the content** around which the second phase of the dissemination strategy is being articulated.

FIGURE 3: POLICY CLOUD PILOT USE CASES: WEB PAGE IMPRESSION

2.3 Exploitable Results

The table below provides an overview of the high-level exploitable results envisaged from the project.

Policy Cloud Result	Target Market	Exploitation Value
Policy modelling	Policy makers / Public authorities	Structural machine-readable representation of policies enabling their monitoring and optimization.
Policy monitoring and evaluation / assessment	Policy makers / Public authorities	Enforcement and runtime adaptation based on aggregated monitoring data from several sources.
Policy collections / clusters analysis tools	Policy makers / Public authorities	Co-creation and optimization of policies utilizing collective knowledge.
Data acquisition tools for policy modelling	Policy makers / Public authorities	Data collection techniques and tools for policy modelling.
Data-driven policy lifecycle management methodology	Policy makers / Public authorities	Incorporation of big data in the policy lifecycle.
Opinion-mining and sentiment analysis algorithms	Social science market/ policy makers / Public authorities	Collection of citizens perceptions on proposed / emerging policies.
Incentives management	Social science market	Increased participation based on varying incentives.
Policy development toolkit	Policy makers / Public authorities	Openness and extensibility by allowing stakeholder to specify their analytics tasks.
Data cleaning mechanisms	Public authorities / Data solution providers	Increased quality of information and reliability of data.
Data modelling and representation tools	Public authorities / Data solution providers	Automation and agility facilitating data integration, linking and interoperability.
Reusable models decoupled from underlying infrastructure	Public authorities / Cloud solution providers / Analytics services	Satisfy privacy / ownership constraints for multi-tenant analytics services.
Data governance model	Data solution providers / public authorities	Ensured data privacy and confidentiality.
Cloud gateways and APIs	Public authorities / cloud providers	Collection of information from different data sources and inclusion of new ones without additional development efforts.
Data Marketplace (possibly integrated within the EOOSC-Hub marketplace)	Cloud providers / Data solution providers	A real-time dataset discovery, indexing and search service enabling users to explore public data that relevant to policy making.

TABLE 3: POLICY CLOUD EXPLOITABLE ASSETS

3 Onboarding End-users

Clearly, an effective end-user engagement strategy works if there is buy-in from the end-user, therefore WP7 is working on building and creating a packaging of the Policy Cloud Solutions (see section 4.1). The consortium will assess the possibility of adding a “policy roundtable” with EC policy officers right after the final project review with a particular interest in the final policy recommendations that will be summarised in the final policy brief.

3.1 Onboarding end-users at national level

The Policy Cloud project is building and implementing the cloud for data-driven policy management with and for the pilot project policy organisations. These organisations are dealing with policy challenges on a local level. Through the co-creation methodology, local potential end-users will be engaged.

The consortium will foster the onboarding of these local end-users by engaging them in their local language through the promotion and celebration of the co-creation workshops (see section 5.4) in the local languages as well as the production of tailored communication materials in the local languages.

In addition, synergies on national level increase the visibility of Policy Cloud and the added value in the pilot projects, and fosters the onboarding end-users.

3.1.1 Onboard in activities Year 1

With the first set of co-creation workshops, engaging local policymakers in the requirements setting for Policy Cloud for policy management tools and services taking place in year 1, a tailored suite of promotional material was developed for the pilots. *Factsheets for policymakers* and *who benefits flyers* in national languages and dedicated visual identities.

FIGURE 4: WHO BENEFITS FLYERS TARGETED AT NATIONAL END-USERS

In year 1, Policy Cloud started with the promotion of pilots via videos dedicated website pages, showcasing video interviews with the pilot and technology providers on the policy challenges to be addressed in each of the pilots (see section 4.5 for more details on the video interviews).

The first two podcasts were delivered, in a series of 4, diving deep into the pilot activities planned to address the policymaking and technical requirements identified via partner interviews, a more detailed description can be found in section 5.5.

3.1.2 Onboarding activities Year 2

The co-creation workshops, further described in section 5.4, are an excellent opportunity to show local communities how Policy Cloud can help them make the transition to data driven policymaking.

The series of Pilot podcasts was completed in the second year of the project, with the publication and promotion of two additional podcasts.

To improve the findability of the pilot tailored promotional material, a dedicated section was integrated in the pilot pages, more details on this improvement in section 4.2.

Policy Cloud showcased two of its pilots at the Major Cities of Europe 2021 event, inspiring cities in Europe to adopt Policy Cloud services:

- Ana Georgieva, form Sofia Municipality, showcased “Urban policy making through analysis of crowdsourced data” at the in the plenary session and via a dedicated video interview with the organisers of the conference.
- At MCE2021, Policy Cloud organised an Innovation Workshop targeted at potential adopters from the public administrations of Major Cities in Europe. During this workshop, Policy Cloud pilots on “Urban policy making through analysis of crowdsourced data” and “Open Policies for Citizens” where showcased, to inspire further adoption. The workshop. Was attended by 70 potential end-users.

FIGURE 5: TWEET BY MAJOR CITIES IN EUROPE, SHOWCASING THE URBANPOLICYMAKING IN SOFIA PILOT IN POLICY CLOUD

In the second wave of co-creation workshops (Q4, 2021) (see section 5.4), WP7 was able to perform Face-to-Face interviews with attendees from the Lombardy Region. The interviews were recorded and will be turned into a video showcasing the “Policies against radicalisation” pilot, as further detailed in section 4.5.

3.1.3 Future steps

In the next months, Policy Cloud will promote the findings form the second wave of pilot co-creation workshops, on the basis of the publishable reports from WP6.

In addition to a Pay Per Click Campaign on social media, to boost the listens on the podcast series, Policy Cloud will look into a series of national language news-items on the final results of the pilots and the impact of Policy Cloud in their (local) communities.

Early 2022 the video with interviews on “Policies against radicalisation” pilot will be published and promoted (see section 4.5).

3.2 Linking pilot policy challenges to EU policy making

In October 2020, the EC approved its new [Open Source Software Strategy 2020-2023](#), a part of the overarching [Digital Strategy of the Commission](#)² and contributing to the Digital Europe programme. Policy Cloud will contribute to this strategy through its use and upstream contributions to open source.

Moreover, with the Data Governance Act of November 2020 the European Commission proposed new rules on data governance. Their aim is to **exploit the high amounts of data created every day, but within**

a trustworthy European framework. These new rules will allow European data to be harnessed and **allow specific European data spaces to benefit society, citizens and companies.** The Commission has proposed nine data spaces in February 2020's [data strategy](#)⁴, ranging from industry to energy, and from health to the European Green Deal. Policy Cloud is exactly the type of instrument which will be able to exploit these large quantities of data in order to benefit society, citizens, and companies, while protecting the data and ensuring GDPR standards are maintained.

Turning the government political vision into actual programmes and actions does not take place in isolation. Political, economic, social and technical factors affect how policies are designed, and who makes them at all levels: global, national and local. D7.2 Market Analysis & Business Potentials⁶, identified different trends that can impact the policy making process and with a focus on big data and cloud capabilities. This analysis is being used as a basis to showcase how Policy Cloud is contributing to the European Policy Landscape by realising the cloud for data-driven policy management in the four policy areas of the pilots.

Policy Cloud communication and dissemination will be linking to EU policy (strategies) addressed in the four Policy Cloud pilot cases to:

- Open up the synergies with Policy Cloud and EU policy strategies allows us to tap into their already established communities.
 - With the BDVA, through Task Force 7 on Application Smart Governance and Smart Cities⁷.
 - With EOSC, through projects such as the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) and EOSC Future, as well as the EOSC Association.
 - With other EC initiatives dealing with smart governance, such DUET and URBANITE projects. And the in 2021 initiated projects IntelComp, DECIDO and AI4PublicPolicy.
 - Connect with European and global networks contributing to data driven policymaking such as OECD and OASC.
 - Connect with European Initiatives dealing with data driven policymaking in such as the DEMETER project.
 - Onboard Impact Creation Board Members experts in the pilot project domains on European level.
- Connect to the pilot communities, forming part of the Policy Cloud target audience on the demand side of small and large policymakers (Small: local level, Large: EU institutions, MS level) as well as on the provider (depending on the EU policy strategy) side. Policy Briefs are the perfect vehicle to elevate the locally identified policy gaps to other regions and levels.

⁶ Policy Cloud, *D7.2 Market Analysis and Business Potentials*, Ester Garrido Gamazo (2020)

⁷ BDVA, Task Force <https://www.bdva.eu/task-force-7>, retrieved 2020-12-21

3.2.1 Onboarding activities Year 1

Up to December 2020 (M12) Policy Cloud worked showcasing how the project and the pilot cases contribute to EC policy making, targeting potential end-users. The following topics were highlighted:

Title news item	EC policy	Policy Cloud Topic
New EC Proposal for Data Sharing and Data Spaces ⁸	The DSA proposal (Proposal for a Regulation on European data governance (Data Governance Act))	Policy Cloud as a Service
Supporting EU Counter-Terrorism Strategy through Data-Driven Policy ⁹	Counter-Terrorism Strategy (EC 2005) European Agenda for Security (2015) Comprehensive Assessment of EU Security Policy (2017)	Policy Cloud Pilot for Policies against Radicalisation
Using big data to Deliver On EU Social Policy Goals ¹⁰	Social Pillar of the Europe 2020 strategy	Policy Cloud Pilots on Open Policies for Citizens and Urban policymaking through analysis of crowdsourced data
EU Digital and Data Strategies Spur Data-driven Policy Pilot ¹¹	The European Digital strategy	Policy Cloud
Policy Cloud Pilot aims to increase effectiveness of EU 'Farm to Fork' policies with big data ¹²	European Green Deal Farm to fork strategy	Policy Cloud Pilot for Intelligent policies for the agri-food sector.

TABLE 4: POLICY CLOUD PILOTS ADDED VALUE LINKED TO EC POLICYMAKING

⁸ Policy Cloud, EC Data Sharing Spaces, <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/news/ec-data-sharing-data-spaces>, retrieved 2020-12-21

⁹ Policy Cloud, Supporting EU counter terrorism strategy through data driven policy <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/news/supporting-eu-counter-terrorism-strategy-through-data-driven-policy>, retrieved 2020-12-21

¹⁰ Policy Cloud, Using Big Data to deliver EU social policy goals, <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/news/using-big-data-deliver-eu-social-policy-goals>, retrieved 2020-12-21

¹¹ Policy Cloud, EU Digital and Data Strategies Spur Data-driven Policy Pilot <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/news/eu-digital-and-data-strategies-spur-data-driven-policy-pilot>, retrieved 2020-12-21

¹² <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/news/policycloud-pilot-aims-increase-effectiveness-eu-farm-fork-policies-big-data>, retrieved 2020-12-21

3.2.2 Onboarding activities Year 2

In the second year of the Policy Cloud project, the consortium continued to link the project to EU policymaking throughout its communication and dissemination activities. In particular we highlight the following activities:

- On 16 February 2021, [Policy Cloud](#), [Cyberwatching](#), [DUET](#), and [URBANITE](#) invited big data and cloud solutions providers and policymakers from industrial, commercial and public realities to an expert briefing¹³ on the perceived scope of the Data Governance Act, the implications for cybersecurity and GDPR, and the practical ramifications for public and business administrations. The webinar, titled “The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations” gathered over 200 registered participants from 22 countries around the globe, 18 from EU countries and 4 non-EU.
- In April 2021, the post event report on “The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations”, was published¹⁴ with recommendations for policymakers. The report has been downloaded 90+ and viewed 100+times.
- The Data Driven Policymaking Week united policymakers, public administrators, decision makers, and social science researchers around the four pilot use cases at the heart of the Policy Cloud project. During the week 26-29 April 2021, four webinars are being hosted by Policy Cloud consortium technology partners and experts from the Policy Cloud Impact Creation Board. Each webinar focuses on one of pilot use cases. The purpose of the webinars was to introduce the pilot use cases and present the technology solutions being developed to address each one's policymaking challenges. Each session described the Pilot's use case, Technology solutions and the EU policy context. The Data Driven Policymaking Week was attended by 99 stakeholders, and 200+ stakeholders had shown interest by registering for the series.

¹³ Policy Cloud, Policy Cloud Pilot aims to increase effectiveness of EU ‘Farm to Fork’ policies with big data <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/events/data-governance-act-and-data-driven-policymaking-impact-and-practical> , retrieved 2020-12-21

¹⁴ Policy Cloud, Report published Data Governance Act <https://www.policycloud.eu/news-events/news/report-published-data-governance-act>, retrieved 2021-12-20

FIGURE 6: POLICY CLOUD PILOTS AND COLLABORATIONS LINKING LOCAL POLICYMAKING CHALLENGES TO THE EU POLICY CONTEXTS.

- In May 2021, Policy Cloud published the post-event-report titled Data Driven Policy Week via ZENODO and its website, the report has been downloaded 100+ and viewed 100+ times up to December 2021¹⁵ (see figure 7).
- In June 2021 Policy Cloud joined efforts within the Data Driven Policy Cluster (see section 3.5), during the event “Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021”, 3 policymaking domains were identified for cross-project discussions. Examples from the local pilots were presented to address commonalities and the wider EU context. The projects are currently working on the definition of three joint policy briefs on:
 - Evidence Based Policies for Health and Social Wellbeing
 - Evidence Based Policies for Climate Change
 - Evidence Based Policies for Urban Mobility

¹⁵ Policy Cloud, Report Published Data Driven Policymaking Week <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/news/report-published-data-driven-policymaking-week> , retrieved 2021-12-20

FIGURE 7: OVERVIEW OF THE IMPACT OF THE POLICY CLOUD DATA DRIVEN POLICY WEEK.

3.2.3 Future steps

In collaboration with the Data Driven Policy Cluster, the consortium will work on a set of policy briefs providing policy makers with recommendations on the gaps identified in the pilots and as well as on a higher level of data-driven policy management and its involvement of citizens. These policy briefs will be aligned with the three cross-project tracks listed above, each discussing the scenario's for related domains from data to policymaking.

In November 2021, the Policy Cloud project established further connections to the H2020 CSA on standardisation, StandICT.eu (see detailed description of this collaboration in D7.7 Standardisation Plan and Activities, M24). This collaboration has already established a StandICT.eu Technical Working Group on Big Data for Smart Cities, to perform a landscape analysis in standardisation on the topic. Recommendations for further standardisation of the domain will be captured in a collaborative white paper, early 2022.

3.3 Policy Cloud in the context of EOSC European Open Science Cloud

Policy Cloud aims to deliver a unique, integrated environment of curated datasets and data management, manipulation, and analysis tools which will be applied to the full lifecycle of policy management in four thematically distinct pilot use cases. These datasets and tools may eventually become accessible to the public forum of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

The EOSC will offer potentially 1.7 million European researchers and 70 million professionals in science, technology, the humanities and social sciences a virtual environment with open and seamless services for storage, management, analysis and re-use of research data, across borders and scientific disciplines by federating existing scientific data infrastructures, currently dispersed across disciplines and the EU Member States.

Engaging with EOSC and the implementation projects, including the flagship project EOSC FUTURE, that aims to start in Q1 of 2021, is essential for the onboarding of end-users. A user engagement and onboarding activity is taking place from the onset of the project, where the users will be codesigning requirements together with the developers of the EOSC, whose policy is to deliver more and better science through open and collaborative knowledge sharing. A particular mention of the engagement of social scientists through the thematically focused project in EOSC ecosystem such as Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC)¹⁶ and Triple¹⁷.

3.3.1 Onboarding activities Year 1

In M12 (December 2020) Policy Cloud had already engaged with EOSC through two of its events:

1. The EOSC-hub week 2020¹⁸ poster presentation
2. A Policy Cloud exhibition booth at the “Realising the European Open Science Cloud. Towards a FAIR research Data Landscape for the Social Sciences and Beyond”¹⁹ conference, (16-19 November 2020), jointly organised by EOSC-hub, FREYA and SSHOC.

¹⁶ SSHOPENCLOUD, SSHOC homepage <https://www.sshopencloud.eu> retrieved 2020-12-21

¹⁷ OPERAS, project homepage <https://operas.hypotheses.org/category/triple>, retrieved 2021-12-20

¹⁸ Policy Cloud, Poster Policy Cloud Big Data distilling services through EOSC <https://policycloud.eu/publications/publications/poster-policy-cloud-big-data-distilling-services-through-eosc>, retrieved 2021-12-20

¹⁹ Policy Cloud, Joint EOSC-hub, FREYA SSHOC event <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/events/joint-eosc-hub-freya-sshoc-event>, retrieved 2020-12-21

FIGURE 8: POLICY CLOUD SERVICES

3.3.2 Onboarding activities Year 2

The Policy Cloud services will be made available via EOSC, through the EGI federated cloud. Policy Cloud will create a major change in how we use data. Public participation through crowdsourcing of data will become far more streamlined, easy and ethically positive. It will enlarge the evidence base for effective policy, making it more predictable. As well as facilitating interoperability through reusable tools. Collaboration with EOSC runs not only via EGI, part of the Policy Cloud consortium and EOSC Association member, working on onboarding the Policy Cloud Services to EOSC, but also via collaboration in the following activities performed in the second year of Policy Cloud:

- The Data Driven Policy Cluster organised a joint workshop on “**Initiatives for better evidence-based policies in the public sector**”, with Ron Dekker, coordinator of the SSHOC and EOSC Future H2020 projects at EGI 2021. The workshop actively engaged EGI and EOSC ecosystems.
- Policy Cloud presented a poster at the EGI 2021 conference, showcasing the services and pilot data for reuse via EOSC.
- At the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit, the cluster onboarded Suzanne Dumouchel, EOSC Association Director and partner in the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud (SSHOC) project, as speaker in the plenary session “From Digital Disruption to Digital Adoption” (see figure below).

FIGURE 9: SUZANNE DUMOUCHEL, EOSC ASSOCIATION DIRECTOR AND PARTNER IN THE SOCIAL SCIENCES AND HUMANITIES OPEN CLOUD (SSHOC) PROJECT, AS SPEAKER IN THE PLENARY SESSION “FROM DIGITAL DISRUPTION TO DIGITAL ADOPTION”

3.3.3 Future steps

Policy Cloud will continue its engagement and collaboration with EOSC, and related projects and align with the current activities, as well as via the onboarding Policy Cloud services and tools to the EOSC via EGI.

Policy Cloud will aim to identify relevant EOSC Task Forces to establish working relationships, via Trust-IT, involved in 2 TFs:

- [TF Researcher Engagement and Adoption](#)
- [TF Defining Funding Models for EOSC](#)

Policy Cloud will continue to engage with the SSHOC project and its direct connection to Social Science Research Infrastructures and communities.

3.4 Impact Creation Board

To proactively support the development of the detailed business plan for the Data Marketplace, the project has set up an external **Impact Creation Board** (ICB), acting as a knowledge and guidance forum and providing advice to the consortium on how to exploit knowledge created by the project. The ICB includes distinguished experts from academia and industry. Specifically, their advice will cover how to promote the uptake and use of Policy Cloud tools, software and guidelines, and how to foster synergies among the different communities researching and developing in the policy making domain.

The consortium will leverage on the member's networks and activities to increase visibility for the Policy Cloud results and activities. All events attended by the ICB members will be highlighted on the Policy Cloud website and social media channels. A dedicated webpage has been set up presenting the first four members of the ICB, and a news-item has been published and promoted to showcase the ICB, its aim and link to the member's networks.

In addition, the consortium will build synergies with the projects the members are involved in where possible, expanding the project network.

3.4.1 Onboarding activities Year 1

In year 1, the ICB had four members, identified key-players in the digital innovation and e-governance field. The consortium was seeking to onboard additional members, decisions makers from areas of the pilot project topics and ensuring gender balance.

FIGURE 10: WEBSITE BANNER PRESENTING THE FIRST FOUR IMPACT CREATION BOARD MEMBERS, LINKING TO A DEDICATED POLICY CLOUD WEBPAGE

3.4.2 Onboarding activities Year 2

In year 2, the consortium onboarded new members to the Policy Cloud Impact Creation Board, strengthening the project with strategic external expertise and seeking gender balance:

- Liliana Carrillo: Founding Director at CollectiveUP and Co-founding Director at the European Digital Development Alliance (EDDA)
- Michela Magas, Chair, Industry Commons Foundation, strategic advisor OntoCommons.eu
- Ray Walshe, Assistant Professor Dublin City University, Director of European Observatory for ICT Standards (EUOS)
- Iskra Yovkova, Head of Corporate Communications and Business Development at Fund of Funds in Bulgaria (FMFIB)

The Impact Creation Board members have been involved in Policy Cloud events such as the Pilot webinar week (see section 3.3), the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021 (see section 3.4) and an internal StandICT.eu and Policy Cloud workshop on standardisation (see D7.7). With the aim to lever on the ICB members' expertise, connect Policy Cloud results and activities to the wider EU policymaking and innovation context. And onboard new communities to the Policy Cloud network.

FIGURE 11: MICHELA MAGAS, POLICY CLOUD ICB MEMBER AS SPEAKER AT THE EVIDENCE BASED POLICY IN EUROPE SUMMIT 2021

3.4.3 Future steps

In year three Policy Cloud will aim to onboard at least one additional ICB member from the pilot policy domains, balancing the policymaking expertise and seeking further gender balance on the Policy Cloud ICB.

The ICB members will be further engaged in communication and stakeholder engagement activities in year, specifically in the project final event.

3.5 Synergies

The creation of synergies is key to the onboarding of end-user through the growing of the community, raising awareness with a joint voice and the fostering of knowledge exchange. With this aim, Policy Cloud will seek to create synergies with European and National initiatives (see section 3.1) focused on data-driven policy making and digital innovation.

Policy Cloud will also seek to engage with Digital Innovation Hubs such as the EOSC-DIH and EUH4D²⁰. These hubs foster collaboration between European initiatives around the data economy and SMEs and start-ups to use and benefit from the federated services and data sources.

3.5.1 Onboarding activities Year 1

3.5.1.1 BIG DATA PILOT DEMO DAYS

During the BDV PPP Summit 2020, Policy Cloud was invited to join the Big Data Pilot Demo Days, joint effort with I-BiDaaS, BigDataStack and Track & Know projects. Policy Cloud showcased the “Policies against Radicalisation” pilot. A total of 513 people registered for the full series of 9 webinars, of which 42 registered for Policy Cloud session, slides and recordings were published and promoted.

FIGURE 12: SAMPLE OF PROMOTIONAL BANNER BIG DATA PILOT DEMO DAYS AT BDV PPP 2020

²⁰ EUHubs, project homepage <https://euhubs4data.eu>, retrieved 2020-12-21

3.5.1.2 BDVA

The **Big Data Value Association** – BDVA, is an industry-driven international not-for-profit organisation with more than 230 **members** all over Europe and a well-balanced composition of large, small, and medium-sized industries as well as research and user organizations.

BDVA/DAIRO focuses on enabling the **digital transformation** of the economy and society through **Data** and **Artificial Intelligence** by advancing in areas such as big data and AI technologies and services, data platforms and data spaces, Industrial AI, data-driven value creation, standardisation, and skills. BDVA/DAIRO has been the private side of the H2020 partnership **Big Data Value cPPP**, it is a **private member of the EuroHPC JU** and is also one of the **founding members of the AI, Data and Robotics Partnership**. BDVA/DAIRO is an open and inclusive community and is always eager to accept new members who share these ambitious objectives.

The **mission of the BDVA** is to **develop the Innovation Ecosystem** that will enable the **data and AI-driven digital transformation in Europe** delivering maximum economic and societal benefit, and, achieving and sustaining Europe’s leadership on **Big Data Value creation** and **Artificial Intelligence**.

Policy Cloud kicked off its collaboration with the BDVA Task force on Smart Governance and Smart Cities at the EBDVF2020, the Smart Society Parallel Session Smart Government with co-creating services using AI and Data, 3 November 2020. Policy Cloud co-organised the session with the BDVA Task Force and the H2020 projects DUET and URBANITE²¹.

FIGURE 13: SMART SOCIETY PARALLEL SESSION SMART GOVERNMENT WITH CO-CREATING SERVICES USING AI AND DATA

²¹ Slides and recordings of “Smart Governance with co-creating services using AI and Data” session at EBDVF2020: <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/events/european-big-data-value-forum-2020>, retrieved 2020-12-21

3.5.2 Onboarding activities Year 2

3.5.2.1 DATA DRIVEN POLICY CLUSTER

Digital technologies have changed the world, today people expect faster, seamless, on-demand services from their providers, and Governance is no exception. For better public services which make life easier for citizens. Public Sector decision making needs to become more agile, breaking down data silos to combine day-to-day tactical decisions with longer term policies and strategies. Disruptive technologies such as Digital Twins, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and High-Performance Computing (HPC) unlock new opportunities for decision making through visualisations, simulations, predictions and intelligence that enhance transparency, increase public support and involvement, and optimise resources, handling data sources too large or complex to be handled by conventional tools.

To support this transformation [AI4PublicPolicy](#), [Decido](#), [DUET](#), [IntelComp](#) and [Policy Cloud](#), five pan-European projects and initiatives dedicated to using cloud for data-driven policy, have joined forces to raise awareness about their cross cutting work on data and cloud-based tools for data-driven decision making.

- The cluster has collaborated on the definition of a joint roadmap²² to describe how the Data Driven Policy Cluster contributes to using the European cloud infrastructure for public administrations, encouraging the public sector decision makers to embrace digital disruption and new innovative technologies in order to make more sustainable policy based on real-time information, predicted impact and citizen input.

²² Policy Cloud, The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations webinar announcement: <https://www.policycloud.eu/news-events/events/data-governance-act-and-data-driven-policymaking-impact-and-practical> , retrieved 2021-12-20

²² Willems, Marieke, Balboni, Paolo, Bettioli, Alberto, Taborda Barata, Martim, Kogut, Pavel, & Campos Cordobes, Sergio. (2021). The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policy Making: Impact and Practical Implementations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4715778>

FIGURE 14: THE DATA DRIVEN POLICY CLUSTER ROADMAP

- The cluster of projects developed an umbrella brand, to illustrate a single point of access for engagement, logo and cluster presentation are available via the Policy Cloud communication kit (see section 4.6).
- To support this Digital Transformation for the Public Sector, Policy Cloud, DECIDO, AI4PublicPolicy, DUET and IntelComp pan-European projects and initiatives dedicated to using cloud for data-driven policy, have joined forces to host Evidence Based Policy Making in Europe Summit 2021²³, a premier conference for government that focuses purely on data and tools for decision making. Together with leading change agents from the European Commission and Local Government the event explored the new decision-making ecosystems being built by cities and administrations, including the use cases being adopted, and the innovative data and tools being adopted for modern policy making. The event took place on virtually on the 9th and 10th of December, 2021, and initiated collaborations with the **EC DGCONNECT, OECD, OASC, ECSA, EOSC Association and BDVA.**

²³ Policy Cloud, Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021 <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/events/evidence-based-policymaking-europe-summit-2021>, retrieved 2021-12-20

Data Driven Policy Cluster
Co-creating digital tools for better governance

Evidence Based Policymaking in Europe Summit: 2021

Day 1: From data to decision making

Join us:
9th December 10 am CET

 Michela Magas Advisor to the EU and G7 and the creator of the concept of the Industry Commons				
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FIGURE 15: EVIDENCE BASED POLICY IN EUROPE SUMMIT 2021, PLENARY KEYNOTE SPEAKERS DAY 1

Data Driven Policy Cluster
Co-creating digital tools for better governance

Evidence Based Policymaking in Europe Summit: 2021

Day 2: from digital disruption to digital adoption

Join us:
10th December 10 am CET

 Natalia Manola CEO of OpenAIRE.			
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FIGURE 16: EVIDENCE BASED POLICY IN EUROPE SUMMIT 2021, PLENARY KEYNOTE SPEAKERS DAY 2

3.5.2.2 BDVA

A collaboration already set in motion in year 1, in the second year of the project Policy Cloud engaged with the BDVA at the EBDVF2021 in the session “Enabling Data Economy for Local Communities” under the umbrella of the “Data Driven Policy Cluster”. To discuss moving from siloed & unconnected initiatives towards interoperability and standardisation of data models and towards open urban data platforms,

which are expected to accelerate local economies. The session was held at the EBDVF2021 on 2 December 2021.

FIGURE 17: DATA DRIVEN POLICY CLUSTER @ENABLING DATA ECONOMY FOR LOCAL COMMUNITIES SESSION (EBDVF2021)

In addition, during the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit, Roberto di Bernardo, BDVA Smart Governance and Smart Cities Task force lead, joined the Plenary Session “From digital disruption to digital adoption”, addressing Data Spaces as key enabler for a Data Society.

3.5.2.3 CYBERWATCHING.EU

Cyberwatching.eu is the European observatory of research and innovation in the field of cybersecurity and privacy. Funded under the European Commission's H2020 programme, this brand-new project will contribute to making the Digital Single Market a safer place by promoting the uptake and understanding of cutting-edge cybersecurity and privacy services which emerge from Research and Innovation initiatives across Europe.

In its mission to democratise cybersecurity for all, the project directly responds to the objectives of the recently signed contractual Public-Private Partnership on cybersecurity (c-PPP) which could become the reference framework for research and innovation initiatives across Europe.

As the online hub for research and innovation in cybersecurity & privacy in Europe, the Cyberwatching.eu website offers European citizens a **single gateway to innovative and trustworthy ICT products, services and software** which take fundamental rights, such as privacy, into consideration.

Policy Cloud collaborated with CyberWatching, DUET and URBANITE projects for a joint webinar “The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations²⁴” on 17 February 2021. Over 200 registrants expressed interest and 120+ stakeholders attended the live discussions. A joint post event report with practical recommendations for policymakers on the Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking²⁵ (see figure 18). Since its publication in April 2021, the report has been downloaded 90+ and viewed 100+ times.

FIGURE 18: WEBINAR DATA GOVERNANCE ACT AND DATA-DRIVEN POLICYMAKING: IMPACT AND PRACTICAL IMPLEMENTATIONS ANNOUNCEMENT

3.5.2.4 DEMETER

The H2020 DEMETER project is a large-scale deployment of farmer-driven, interoperable smart farming-IoT (Internet of Things) based platforms, delivered through a series of 20 pilots across 18 countries (15

²⁴ Policy Cloud, The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations webinar announcement: <https://www.policycloud.eu/news-events/events/data-governance-act-and-data-driven-policymaking-impact-and-practical> , retrieved 2021-12-20

²⁵ Willems, Marieke, Balboni, Paolo, Bettiol, Alberto, Taborda Barata, Martim, Kogut, Pavel, & Campos Cordobes, Sergio. (2021). The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policy Making: Impact and Practical Implementations. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4715778>

EU countries). Involving 60 partners, DEMETER adopts a multi-actor approach across the value chain (demand and supply), with 25 deployment sites, 6,000 farmers and over 38,000 devices and sensors being deployed.

During the Data Driven Policy Week, connections were made with the DEMETER project Mariano Navarro - HEAD OF ICT/R&D at TRAGSA, project partner in DEMETER, who provided the EU policy context for the Policy Cloud “Intelligent policies of the food value chain” pilot.

FIGURE 19: PROMOTIONAL BANNER DATA DRIVEN POLICYMAKING FOR THE FOOD VALUE CHAIN

3.5.3 Future steps

In the third year of the project, the Policy Cloud consortium will continue to build on the synergies established in the previous periods, more concretely we define future steps per collaboration below.

EOSC:

- Wrapping up the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021, Policy Cloud will drive the publication and promotion of a post-event report with the main conclusions and recommendations from the discussions on data management as well as technical interoperability topics.
- As active member of the Data Driven Policy Cluster, will continue to align with the 5 projects on cross-cutting interoperability in cloud technology and data management aspects. Policy Cloud will explore the possibility of a joint report and webinar on this topic.
- In addition, Policy Cloud will invite the cluster projects to join the StandICT.eu TWG on Big Data for Smart Cities, to start activities early 2022.

BDVA:

- At the time of writing this deliverable, exchanges have gone on with the chairs of the ICT rolling Plan of Standardisation and the Policy Cloud partners have provided content to the new dedicated chapter entitled “Data Economy” ready for the ICT Rolling Pan 2022 edition. Moreover, the definition of the Technical Working Group on Big Data for Smart Cities is being finalised with a number of key players from Policy Cloud consortium to drive this forward.

4 Communications and Dissemination Plan

4.1 Visual Identity & Branding

With the aim of building a strong identity, a branding has been set in place that visually displays the key outputs and activities in the project, defined in the D7.1 Initial Publication Package. A branding guide²⁶ has been created to guide the use of the Policy Cloud logo, colours, and fonts.

FIGURE 20: BRAND MANUAL DEFINING USE OF LOGO AND COLOUR PALETTE

26

4.1.1 Branding activities Year 1

Tailored branding for each of the pilots was developed with dedicated image (see figure 3 in section 2.2) and icon (see figure 8), to be used in communication on and for each of the pilots. Increasing visibility of these pilots on National and European level through the use of both English and national languages for each of the pilots (see figure 4, in section 3.1).

FIGURE 21: ICONS FOR POLICY CLOUD PILOTS

Dedicated icons were defined for the Policy Cloud services, as shown in the figure below, and have been implemented in the produced communication material.

FIGURE 22: ICONS DESIGNED FOR POLICY CLOUD SERVICES

All communication materials developed on the website, in printable and online format for events, in videos and on social media, are Policy Cloud branded with indicated icons, images and colours. These materials contribute to strengthening this visual identity and increase the visibility of Policy Cloud as a reference for European Cloud environments for data-driven policy management. A sample is included below to showcase the strengthening of the Policy Cloud visual identity.

The services were branded individually, and already used in printable and online communication material, videos, the website, and social media banners.

FIGURE 23: IMPRESSIONS OF THE POLICY CLOUD BRANDED COMMUNICATION MATERIAL

4.1.2 Branding activities Year 2

The Policies against radicalisation pilot’s image was changed to an image of a riot, to represent radicalisation and the image for Open Data Policies for Citizens was changed to a crowd of pedestrians in London, to represent the citizens of London, the city where the pilot is being run.

A suite of icons has been delivered for the Policy Cloud marketplace, visually branding the offerings to policymakers and citizens, to be used in the next release. As well as three infographics, each visually representing a user journeys through the Policy Cloud Data Marketplace, as defined in D7.5 Data Marketplace Software Prototype93. These user journeys are prepared for the dedicated promotion of the Policy Cloud Data Marketplace planned early year 3.

FIGURE 24: SAMPLE OF ONE OF THE THREE POLICY CLOUD DATA MARKETPLACE USER JOURNEY INFOGRAPHICS

4.1.3 Next steps

In Year 3 Policy Cloud will be putting a catalogue of components & services which can be adopted by other projects or organisations. This catalogue will be graphically designed with appropriate icons and branding,

The Policy Development Toolkit, the front-end instrument which will be used by Policy Makers, will undergo a graphical makeover, both to increase usability and visual appeal.

4.2 Policy Cloud Website

The Policy Cloud website is the Gateway to its project and network channels for the wider dissemination of the project activities and achievements. The website also acts as a knowledge hub for its publicly available reports and scientific publications.

4.2.1 Website activities Year 1

In M1 (January 2020) the project landing page went live, followed by the project website launch in M4 (April 2020). The site explains [what Policy Cloud aims to achieve](#) and [links to the project social media channels: Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube](#) and the repository service [ZENODO](#) where Policy Cloud uploads all deliverables that can be publicly shared. Between M4 – M12 the website constantly expanded. There is a pilot's section with a main page as well as an individual page for each pilot. Under the resources menu all important public resources of the project can be found including Deliverables, Publications, Presentations, Posters, Videos, Podcasts, and the Communications Kit. In M12 (December 2020) a page was set up for the Impact Creation Board, including short bios of each of the members. The Policy Cloud website is the central hub for all communication and dissemination activities.

FIGURE 25: IMPRESSIONS OF THE HOME-PAGE (LEFT) AND DELIVERABLES PAGE (RIGHT) ON THE POLICY CLOUD WEBSITE

Social media posts always include a call to action which point people towards relevant sections of the website. This has been successful leading to long session times and low bounce rates for users. At M12, The Policy Cloud website had received an average of 200 visits (sessions) per month.

FIGURE 26: POLICY CLOUD WEBSITE DASHBOARD

4.2.2 Website activities Year 2

In response to reviewers' comments, the scientific publications were made more visible on the website. This was done by giving the scientific papers their own menu option under outreach. Along with this change a general reorganisation of the menus and ordering of content was undertaken, grouping all relevant materials produced by the Policy Cloud project under the "Outreach" menu item. Outreach has 6 submenus:

- Scientific Publications includes all academic papers published by the project
- Deliverables includes all the public project deliverables
- Reports, Presentations & Posters includes all non-scientific reports published, such as event reports and policy briefs, event presentations, and posters that have been produced for the project
- Articles & Blogs include various articles and blogs about Policy Cloud which have been posted on other websites
- Videos & Podcasts includes all the videos and podcasts which have been produced by the project
- Communications Kit includes essential communications materials such as the project logo, project presentation template, local language factsheets, who benefits info sheet, and brand guidelines.

FIGURE 27: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS PAGE, ALL ENTRIES ARE FILTERABLE FOR TYPE OF PUBLICATION

Two new pages and submenus were also added to "News & Events."

- Policy Cloud Newsletters gathers together all the newsletter have been sent to the Policy Cloud community
- Press Clippings gathers together various press and news media articles about Policy Cloud

FIGURE 28: PRESS CLIPPINGS PAGE

Finally, a new version the Join the Community page was created entitled “Be Part of Policy Cloud.” The new page provides a narrative explaining why user would want to be part of the Policy Cloud community and co-creation

Would you like to be an active part of the Policy Cloud co-creation process?

Can you take part?

Why join?

We are establishing a community for public administrators, policymakers and stakeholders involved in policy making, to support us and participate in the co-creation activities of the project.

We are looking for policy makers, public administrators, and experts from academia, industry and citizen organizations interested in policymaking.

- Learn about the use of big data for evidence based policymaking
- Be part of our co-creation process. Influence the development of the platform
- Selected users given early access to the Policy Cloud platform

Support our innovative co-creation process!

FIGURE 29: SAMPLE OF THE BE PART OF POLICY CLOUD PAGE

4.2.3 Next steps

The main website project for Y3 will be to create a catalogue of Policy Cloud’s services and components which can be onboarded by other projects and organisations. This will include code, where things are open source, and contact addressed, where components or services will have a cost.

4.3 Social Media Channels

The Policy Cloud social media strategy is centred on **Twitter** and **LinkedIn**, and both official accounts were launched on the road to the kick-off meeting in Madrid, Spain in line with the visual design of the rest of our communications kit.

The Twitter account **@Policy CloudEU**²⁷ and the LinkedIn page **Policy Cloud EU**²⁸ are mainly employed in order to establish community, regularly engage with stakeholders, connect with relevant accounts or

²⁷ Twitter, Policy Cloud account <https://twitter.com/PolicyCloudEU>, retrieved 2020-12-21

²⁸ LinkedIn, Policy Cloud addount <https://www.linkedin.com/company/policycloudeu>, retrieved 2020-12-21

individuals, promote regular news items and (virtual) events Policy Cloud is attending or organising, as well as for the dissemination of the project’s outcomes and updates.

4.3.1 Social Media activities Year 1

In M1-M6 (January 2020 – June 2020) some relevant hashtags and topics with which to interact on our social media channels were identified in order to increase our reach, such as **#policymaking**, **#policymanagement**, **#sustainability**, **#foodsafety**, **#healthcare**, **#employment**, **#radicalisation**, **#cohesionpolicy**, **#sustainableurbandevelopment**, **#migration**.

FIGURE 30: SAMPLE OF BRANDED, CONTENT RICH SOCIAL MEDIA POSTS

Numbers were well on track to reach the projects social media KPIs of 500 Tweets, 500 Twitter followers and 800 LinkedIn followers. Policy Cloud had Tweeted 210 times, and had 133 followers on Twitter. On LinkedIn, Policy Cloud already had more than half the target number of followers with 503.

In order to continually engage these communities, social media is updated regularly. Four tweets are sent per week, and at least one Status Update on LinkedIn. All social media posts are accompanied by an appealing graphic and a call to action, which guides users to relevant material on the Policy Cloud website. Social media posts generally point to news articles or events posted on the Policy Cloud website. Policy Cloud social media is tracked on a weekly basis, see section 6.2.

To continue the growth of the Policy Cloud community, important multipliers are targeted for the different stakeholder communities. Through tagging these multipliers in relevant posts, it is more likely that they will share or retweet Policy Cloud to their communities. Some of these targeted multipliers can be found in the below table:

Multiplier	Platforms	Description	Community	Stakeholder Category
	Twitter: @EITCI	European Information Technologies Certification Institute - Disseminating and Attesting Digital Skills - Supporting Development of Information Technologies	14.6K	R&I, Cloud and Big data
	Twitter: @EoscSecretariat LinkedIn: EOSCsecretariat	We support the #EOSC Governance as we work openly and inclusively with communities to co-create the European #OpenScience #Cloud	1.7K	EOSC, R&I, Cloud
	Twitter: @Radicalisation	Gathers high-quality academic research on radicalisation, extremism and fundamentalism and makes it easily accessible to a broader public.	5.5k	Policy - radicalisation
	Twitter: @RANEurope LinkedIn: Radicalisation Awareness Network - RAN	Connecting frontline practitioners from across Europe. Established by @EUHomeAffairs.	10.4k	Policy - radicalisation
	Twitter: @EUAgri	Food, farming, and the future of agriculture. Sowing the seeds of EU Agriculture & Rural Development policy.	77.5k	Policy - food
	Twitter: @SSHOpenCloud LinkedIn: SSHOC - Social Sciences and	SSHOC provides a fully-fledged Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cloud where data, tools, and training are available to	1.3K	EOSC, Social Science

Multiplier	Platforms	Description	Community	Stakeholder Category
	Humanities Open Cloud	#SSH communities as part of the #EOSC		
	Twitter: @BDVA_PPP LinkedIn: BDVA - Big Data Value Association	Big Data Value is the Public Private ecosystem around Big Data in Europe. In 2020 Policy Cloud took part in the EBDVF organised by BDV.	3.1K	Big Data, R&I, AI, Cloud

TABLE 5: SAMPLE OF STRATEGIC CONNECTIONS TO MULTIPLIERS ON THE POLICY CLOUD KEY PILLARS

An official Policy Cloud YouTube account²⁹ was set up to upload videos as well as a Soundcloud account³⁰ to upload podcasts which are then embedded on web pages and shared across other channels, see section 4.5 for more details.

4.3.2 Social Media activities Year 2

In year 2 of the Policy Cloud project, social media activities built on the strategy already set in place in year 1, to widely disseminate project results and activities. Stakeholders and followers were actively engaged via social media in the evolution of Policy Cloud services and pilot implementation.

In numbers, the Policy Cloud social media pages are followed by 1.803 followers on LinkedIn and 322 on Twitter by M24 of the project. This shows an increase of 334% of the Policy Cloud social media community, compared to Y1.

The community has grown through an active one-to-one contact scouting on social media, direct invites to project events created on social media and the live tweeting during events.

4.3.3 Next steps

Looking at the considerations in section 4.3.2, an essential first step is undoubtedly LinkedIn. Given the substantial increase in followers, it is necessary to exploit the interest and create different content based on the two different social media preferences. This strategy does not affect Twitter activity as it will simply differentiate the content disseminated to get the best from each social network.

These manoeuvres should help us to achieve the KPI's proposed for the following year, see section 6.1.

²⁹ YouTube, Policy Cloud account <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC4iwXbaPPSY9AmYF67mWGng>, retrieved 2020-12-21

³⁰ SoundCloud, Policy Cloud account <https://soundcloud.com/user-683096329>, retrieved 2020-12-21

In addition, in year 3 Policy Cloud will use budget originally planned for physical events, and at M24 underspent due to COVID-19 restrictions, to boost the numbers on social media with paid campaigns of the in-depth pilot podcasts.

4.4 Newsletters

Newsletters aim to raise awareness on Policy Cloud results and activities, and recruit Policy Cloud community members. The newsletter sign-up is made visible via the homepage and is reminded in the regular project updates and social media activities. The newsletter is branded with the project visual identity.

4.4.1 Newsletter activities Year 1

During year 1 the project worked on building its network and to be ready to launch its newsletter series. Newsletter sign-ups come from social media activities, website sign-ups, events and surveys. In total the consortium will send out a total of 10 newsletters.

4.4.2 Newsletter activities Year 2

As of M23 (November 2021) there have been 5 newsletters sent to the Policy Cloud community of 194 recipients. Events have been a key method of growing the Policy Cloud community, with 90 new subscribers added to the newsletter after the joint Data Governance Act event in February, thanks to the strategy of placing a newsletter signup option in the event registration forms. At the same time the newsletter has been an effective way to increase registrations to various Policy Cloud events, leading to a strategy of sending a newsletter in the lead up to Policy Cloud events.

Hello!

Welcome to this summer edition of the Policy Cloud newsletter. We want to let you know about the content we have produced as well as the events we have coming up the rest of this year!

Evidence Based Policymaking in Europe 2021

The convergence of Cloud, Big Data and AI has already resulted in major transformation across Government services, yet the process of policy making itself is often left behind. Join Policy Cloud, Decido, AI4PublicPolicy, BDVA, DUET and Intelcomp at the virtual Evidence Based Policy Making in Europe event to explore major challenges, trends and opportunities to

FIGURE 31: A MAJOR EVENT BEING HIGHLIGHTED IN A RECENT EDITION OF THE POLICY CLOUD NEWSLETTER

A dedicated page was added on the website for those who want to read previous editions of the newsletter, as well as a new improved newsletter sign up page, giving a better narrative explanation as to why people should become part of the Policy Cloud community.

4.4.3 Next steps

In Y3 Policy Cloud will continue to grow the community of newsletter subscribers to ensure that the impact of the project is enhanced especially as more concrete results become available towards the end of the project. Regular newsletters will be sent out to maintain engagement and interest in the project.

4.5 Videos

Based on interviews conducted with partners during the Policy Cloud kick-off meeting, a variety of branded videos have been created to raise awareness of the pilot use cases, tools and services and launch the project. These six videos are featured on the Policy Cloud website and dedicated YouTube channel website, offered to partners for use in on- and offline stakeholder engagement activities, and promoted consistently on social media. In addition to the YouTube channel, a dedicated webpage has been set in place for the videos.

During the first year, Policy Cloud has organised two joint online events, the recordings of these session are also available on the Policy Cloud website to encourage reuse.

The KPI contractually set in the GA is for the consortium to deliver 4 Generic videos over the 36 months – the first that may be carried out in the first reporting period, on the overall objectives & principal assets of Policy Cloud with a duration of 40 seconds, and one video on each of the pilot cases developed and the impact achieved of assets introduced as part of the EOSC service catalogue. Over 200 individual views to the videos upload onto YouTube channel.

4.5.1 Social Media activities Year 1

In Year 1 the consortium worked hard to achieve this KPI, with a total of six tailored promotional videos on YouTube, which received over 620 views all together (including the 25 views of the webinar recordings).

FIGURE 32: POLICY CLOUD YOUTUBE CHANNEL

4.5.2 Video activities Year 2

In year 2, the total number of videos created and uploaded to YouTube has increased and now counts 25, overall counting 5.846 views.

To improve access, WP7 decided to categorise the videos in playlists (see figure 33):

- Dissemination: 6 scripted, edited and branded promotional videos
- Data Driven Policymaking week session recordings
- Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021 session recordings
- Webinars

FIGURE 33: POLICY CLOUD YOUTUBE PLAYLIST WITH 4 CATEGORIES

In the second series of co-creation workshops, WP7 was able to perform video interviews with policymakers and potential end-users, attending the Policies against Radicalization in the Lombardy Region. These video interviews will be edited to a pilot dissemination video, branded with the Policy Cloud look & feel, pilot icons and images.

4.5.1 Next steps

In the third year, the technical work of the project will be ready to be showcased in demos to guide potential end-users through the functionalities of the Policy Cloud services. First steps have been undertaken for a demo on Policy Cloud and the management of data of the Global Terrorism Data Base (see figure below).

FIGURE 34: SAMPLE OF THE POLICY CLOUD DEMO GRAPHIC VISUALISATION OF MANAGEMENT OF DATA FROM THE GLOBAL TERRORISM DATA BASE

In 2022, the consortium will work to increase the visibility of the developed videos during the co-creation workshops to be delivered in WP6, third part events, news-items and social media promotion. In addition, the consortium will seek to develop a video on the impact achieved of assets introduced as part of the EOSC service catalogue.

4.6 Communications Toolkit

The communication kit is published on the website for all partners and stakeholder to facilitate the promotion of Policy Cloud results and activities.

4.6.1 Communication Toolkit Year 1

The Communications Toolkit includes all standard reference material and branded collateral of potential use to project partners in their dissemination activities including:

- Logos
- Fact sheet for policy makers
- Who benefits flyer
- General presentation
- Introductory press release
- Other promotional collateral

Policy Cloud pilots contribute to the co-creation of the final and tailored implementation of the Cloud environment for data-driven policy management. The pilots address policy issues at local level, and engage local stakeholders in their national languages. The consortium engages these stakeholders in their national languages in the co-creation workshops, organised at pilot level. To onboard these potential end-users (see section 3.1), the consortium translated the communication material developed targeted at end-users and to be disseminated at the pilot workshops. In year 1 the “factsheet for policy makers” and the “who benefits flyer” have already been translated into three of the four local languages of the pilots and included in the Communication Kit for reuse.

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About Resources Pilots Services Who Benefits News & Events

Communication kit

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Flyers Who Benefits

ATTACHMENT	SIZE
Who Benefits Open Data Policies UK.pdf	4.61 MB
Who Benefits Policies against Radicalisation Italy_compressed.pdf	220.6 KB
Who Benefits Urban Policymaking Bulgaria_compressed.pdf	992.67 KB
Who Benefits Intelligent policies for the food value chain Spain.pdf	5.05 MB

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Factsheets for Policy Makers

ATTACHMENT	SIZE
FACTSHEET_NOV20_EN.pdf	418.13 KB
FACTSHEET_NOV20_ES.pdf	444.4 KB
FACTSHEET_NOV20_JT.pdf	408.21 KB

Realising the European Cloud for Data-Drive Policy Management_PPT

ATTACHMENT	SIZE
PolicyCLOUD_PPT_Nov2020.ppt	9.85 MB

Pop Up

ATTACHMENT	SIZE
Popup_january2020.pdf	2.93 MB

Branding

ATTACHMENT	SIZE
POLICY_CLOUD_Guideline_Sep2020.pdf	489.42 KB
policy_cloud_logo_compact_2.jpg	478.07 KB
Policy_cloud_logo_compact.jpg	1.82 MB
policy_cloud_logo_extended_2.jpg	464.76 KB
Policy_cloud_logo_extended.jpg	1.78 MB

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FIGURE 35: POLICY CLOUD COMMUNICATION TOOLKIT ON THE PROJECT WEBSITE

4.6.2 Communication Toolkit Year 2

Several activities took place in the communication toolkit to support dissemination of Policy Cloud activities and results.

Policy Cloud lead the definition and design of an umbrella brand for the Data Driven Policy Cluster, building a recognisable visual identity for the group of 5 e-governance projects (see section 3.5) as shown in the figure below.

FIGURE 36: SAMPLE OF THE DATA DRIVEN POLICY CLUSTER BRANDING

For the joint event, a joint presentation template, and cluster presentation were developed and made available via the Policy Cloud Communication kit. A dedicated virtual background and a suite of cluster branded social media banners were designed and used by all projects in the event promotion.

FIGURE 37: VIRTUAL BACKGROUND WITH BRANDING OF THE EVENT AND CLUSTER

4.6.3 Next steps

With the expectations of reopening of physical events after the COVID-19 pandemic, new formats of communication material could be considered, moving from purely digital to a more material one. The WP7 team will consider the creation of Policy Cloud branded booklets showcasing its final results and pilot implementation stories, as well as Policy Cloud branded and sustainable cups such as the ones sampled in the picture below.

FIGURE 38: SAMPLE OF POLICY CLOUD BRANDED SUSTAINABLE CUPS, POTENTIAL PROMOTIONAL MATERIAL FOR THE FINAL PROJECT EVENT

4.7 Publications

The Policy Cloud website provides access to the Policy Cloud publications such as scientific papers and poster presentations at conferences, for the community to consult and reuse. Where allowed, the Policy Cloud publications are uploaded to ZENODO, to increase visibility, assign a DOI and monitor impact e.g. downloads, views and tweets of each publication.

4.7.1 Publication activities Year 1

The KPI set for the 36 months of the Policy Cloud project are 12 articles by specialised and/or general media outlets. At month 12, the consortium had 2 publications on CORDIS and was planning two joint publications per year with like-minded H2020 projects during the years 2020 and 2021.

FIGURE 39: SAMPLE OF POLICY CLOUD WEBPAGE PUBLICATIONS, POSTERS AND PRESENTATIONS

4.7.2 Publication activities Year 2

One of the recommendations received in the first project review was to make scientific publications more visible and easier to find on the website.

The main way this has been achieved was by separating them from other project publications, and giving them their own page. This page is also the first submenu under “Outreach as can be seen in the figure below. News pieces and social media posts are also created for each scientific publication, and a new section in the newsletter lists the most recent scientific publications, linking to their specific news on the website.

FIGURE 40: POLICY CLOUD OUTREACH SUBMENU

Policy Cloud also published 2 post event reports in Y2.

- The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policy Making: Impact and Practical Implementations was published on Zenodo 23 April 2021 as a result of a joint webinar between Policy Cloud and three other EC funded projects, Cyberwatching, DUET, and URBANITE. The central message of the report are seven recommendations for SMEs, policymakers, and public administrations in preparing for the implementation of the Data Governance Act. The report has had 92 views and 83 downloads as of M23.
- Data-Driven Policymaking Week was published 14 May 2021 as a result of a four-day event organised by Policy Cloud to highlight the work of the four Pilots. The report outlines the policymaking challenge, the data required and the Policy Cloud solution for each of the four pilot areas covered by Policy Cloud. It also includes recommendations for policymakers from each of the speakers. The report has had 114 views and 99 downloads as of M23.

Policy Cloud partners have produced 9 scientific articles in the first two years of the project, 3 of them in review and publication process. The table below lists the scientific publications up to date.

Title of the scientific publication	DOI	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Date
Policy Cloud: Analytics as a Service Facilitating Efficient Data-Driven Public Policy Management	10.1007/978-3-030-49161-1_13	Kyriazis D. et al.	Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI 2020) Springer Journal	29/05/2020
An Evaluation of Neural Machine Translation and Pre-trained Word Embeddings in Multilingual Neural Sentiment Analysis	10.1109/PIC50277.2020.9350849	George Manias, Argyro Mavrogiorgou, Athanasios Kiourtis, Dimosthenis Kyriazis	2020 IEEE International Conference on Progress in Informatics and Computing (PIC)	16/02/2021
An Optimized KDD Process for Collecting and Processing Ingested and Streaming Healthcare Data	10.1109/ICICS52457.2021.9464551	Argyro Mavrogiorgou, Athanasios Kiourtis, George Manias, Dimosthenis Kyriazis	2021 12th International Conference on Information and Communication Systems (ICICS)	28/06/2021
Adjustable Data Cleaning towards Extracting Statistical Information	10.3233/SHTI210332	Argyro Mavrogiorgou, Athanasios Kiourtis, George Manias, Dimosthenis Kyriazis	EFMI 2020 Special Topic Conference (EFMI STC)	27/05/2021
SemAI: A Novel Approach for Achieving Enhanced Semantic	https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-79150-6_54	George Manias, Argyro Mavrogiorgou, Athanasios Kiourtis, Dimosthenis Kyriazis	17th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence	22/06/2021

Title of the scientific publication	DOI	Authors	Title of the journal or equivalent	Date
Interoperability in Public Policies			Applications and Innovations (AIAI)	
Parallel Query Processing in a Polystore Distributed and Parallel Databases	TBA	Boyan Kolev, Oleksandra Levchenko, Esther Pacitti, Patrick Valduriez, Ricardo Jimenez-Peris, Pavlos Kranas, Marta Patino-Martinez		
Creating Web-based, Meta-Simulation Environments for Social Dynamics in an Interactive Framework for Public Policy Analysis and Design	10.1109/DS-RT52167.2021.9576158	Nikitas M. Sgouros, Dimosthenis Kyriazis	https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/xpl/conhome/9575167/proceeding	27-29/9/2021
Elastic Scalable Transaction Processing in LeanXcale	TBA	Ricardo Jimenez-Peris, Diego Burgos-Sancho, Francisco Ballesteros, Patricio Martinez, Marta Patiño-Martinez, Patrick Valduriez	Submitted – awaiting review	
Real-Time Kafka-based Topic Modeling and Categorization of Tweets	TBA	George Manias, Argyro Mavrogiorgou, Athanasios Kiourtis, Dimitris Kakomitas, Dimosthenis Kyriazis	2021 IEEE International Conference on Progress in Informatics and Computing (PIC-2021)	17-19/12/2021

TABLE 6: SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS MADE BY THE POLICY CLOUD CONSORTIUM

4.7.3 Future steps

This multiplatform strategy will continue to be implemented in Year 3 of the project assuring that any relevant stakeholders are able to access and read the scientific publications related to Policy Cloud.

Policy Cloud will continue to publish post-event reports, including conclusions and recommendations for data-driven policymaking, to extend the impact of individual events beyond the days of the event itself and beyond the event’s original audience.

Partners will continue to publish scientific papers, targeting both the technology and governance domains.

5 Policy Cloud workshops, webinars, third party events and podcasts

The organization of a series of Webinars, Workshops, podcasts and presentations at third part events, is strategically crucial to broaden the outreach of the project and to start new synergies with other projects and initiatives on European and national pilot level.

5.1 COVID-19

Under the current COVID-19 restrictions, it is vital to find new forms of engagement and ways to support uptake right across the policy making and innovation technology community. In this regard, Webinars will play a vital role as a productive replacement of face-to-face events to keep the community current with the project's advancements and results, as well as to onboard new members.

5.1.1 Mitigation Actions Year 1

In December 2020 (M12), the consortium needed to be very agile in changing its behaviour due to COVID-19 and had carried out a number of actions to mitigate this.

Challenge faced due to COVID-19	Mitigation action taken - year 1
Project promotion at third part events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Digital poster presentation at EOSC-hub week 2020 -Digital poster submission at German EC Presidency 2020 event "Revitalising Democracy in times of Division", event was cancelled. -Virtual paper presentation at AIAI2020 -Virtual presentation at EGI2020 -Virtual exhibition booth at Realising EOSC (joint event EOSC-hub, SSHOC and FREYA)
Creation of synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Webinar in online #BigDataPilotDemosDays series with BigDataStack, I-BiDaaS and Track& Know at the virtual BDV PPP 2020 summit -Virtual session with DUET, URBANITE and the BDV Task Force 7 on Smart governance and smart cities at the EBDVF2020
Co-Creation workshops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -first two co-creations workshops were celebrated in a digital format. -tailored and translated into local languages promotional material was provided to pilot communities in digital format.

Increasing visibility of the project, during its first year, the year of the pandemic.	-start of podcast series, as an alternative for people to learn about the project at moments that suit them best, through in-depth interviews.
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TABLE 7: MITIGATION MECHANISMS FOR COVID-19 CHALLENGES

5.1.2 Mitigation Actions Year 2

The activities carried out in Year 2 by the Consortium to mitigate the impact of COVID-19 on the project can be consulted in the table below:

Challenge faced due to COVID-19	Mitigation action taken - year 2
Project promotion at third part events	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Digital poster presentation at EGI 2021 -Virtual paper presentation at AIAI2021, IEEE2021, PIC2021 -Virtual plenary presentation at MCE1 -Virtual exhibition booth at MCE2021
Creation of synergies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations webinar with CyberWatching.eu, DUET and Urbanite - The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations report with CyberWatching.eu, DUET and Urbanite - Data Driven Policymaking Week series of 4 webinars with DEMETER, and ICB members from: CollectiveUP & European Digital Development Alliance, TNO, Lisbon Council for Economic Competitiveness & Social Renewal -Joining efforts with DUET, Intelcomp, DECIDO and AI4PublicPolicy in the Data Driven Policy Cluster to organise the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021 -Jointly defined, published and promoted Data Driven Policy Cluster Roadmap -EGI2021 conference session titled “Initiatives for better evidence-based policies in the public sector”, organised by Policy Cloud in the Data Driven Policy Cluster and connection made with EOSC Future & SSHOC.
Co-Creation workshops	-second series of co-creations workshops were celebrated in a hybrid format.

<p>Increasing visibility of the project, during its first year, the year of the pandemic.</p>	<p>-2 additional podcasts in the series of Policy Cloud pilot podcasts, as an alternative for people to learn about the project at moments that suit them best, through in-depth interviews.</p>
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TABLE 8: MITIGATION MECHANISMS FOR COVID-19 CHALLENGES CONTINUED IN YEAR 2

5.1.3 Future steps

In 2022, the third year of the Policy Cloud project, the world is still facing the COVID-19 pandemic with different policies across countries affecting physical events. This means that the Policy Cloud consortium will remain flexible towards the organisation of events and will continue to look at the virtual conferences to attend and present the Policy Cloud results and activities.

WP7 will explore the possibilities of expanding the podcast series with interviews with members of the ICB, connecting Policy Cloud work to the European landscape of digital transformation in the public sector.

5.2 Policy Cloud workshops

The consortium will organise two annual events (T7.3) to widely disseminate the project results and activities for wider uptake. In addition, under task 7.5 Innovation Management an additional two innovation workshops are planned, inviting potential adopters of Policy Cloud, where they will have a discussion playground. The innovation workshops are not within the scope of this deliverable and are reported on in the T7.5 deliverables.

5.2.1 Policy Cloud activities Year 1

In Year 1, the consortium decided to hold the first workshop in Year 2 and the second one in Year 3. The current COVID-19 pandemic travel restrictions will be considered when planning these workshops in an on- or offline format. The consortium will look at co-location at relevant third-party conferences targeting potential end-users (see section 6 for an overview of the KPIs).

5.2.2 Policy Cloud activities Year 2

Here we report on 2 main events organised by Policy Cloud, and both of the events were organised in the context of the Data Driven Policy Cluster. Both activities have been extensively described in section 3.5. Here we want to report on the impact and rationale behind the events.

5.2.2.1 EVIDENCE BASED POLICY IN EUROPE SUMMIT 2021

Policy Cloud, DECIDO, AI4PublicPolicy, DUET and IntelComp pan-European projects and initiatives dedicated to using cloud for data-driven policy, have joined forces to host Evidence Based Policy Making in Europe, a premier conference for government that focuses purely on data and tools for decision making. Together with leading change agents from the European Commission and Local Government the event explored the new decision-making ecosystems being built by cities and administrations,

including the use cases being adopted, and the innovative data and tools being adopted for modern policy making.

Taking place virtually on the 9th and 10th of December 2021, here we list what attendees were to expect:

- **Use Cases:** We've asked our speakers to bring real-life examples of how they are transforming the traditionally slow deliberative policy making process in the fields of health, climate change and mobility, to one that is more agile and responsive. Hear directly from cities themselves on how they are developing better evidence-based policies which adapt as new data comes to light, and which are trusted and contributed to by relevant stakeholders who feel engaged in the process.
- **Tools:** See how city managers and policy makers are co-creating data-driven decision-making ecosystems with cutting edge tools which enable them to visualise, analyse and even predict the complex impact of decisions across multiple domains, time and space. Be hands-on with AI, big data and digital twin demos and be inspired by what you could potentially achieve for your administration.
- **Strategies:** Learn how to manage legal, ethical and standards challenges and constraints in our increasingly digital world. From best practices to principles and legislation our speakers will help you understand and navigate the complex environment in pragmatic ways that will get you started on your journey.

FIGURE 41: ANNOUNCEMENT OF THE EVIDENCE BASED POLICY IN EUROPE SUMMIT 2021

A total of 236 people registered for the event from the following stakeholder categories:

FIGURE 42: STAKHOLDER DISTRIBUTION FOR THE EVIDENCE BASED POLICY IN EUROPE SUMMIT REGISTRANTS

On day 1 the cluster engaged a total of 112 participants, focusing on policymakers in the domains of Climate Change, Health and Social Wellbeing and Urban Mobility. Day one also made connections with key players in the field, EC DG CONNECT, OECD, ECSA, Informatie Vlaanderen and IndustryCommons.

FIGURE 43: SESSION BANNERS OF THE POLICY FOCUSED DAY 1 AT THE EVIDENCE BASED POLICY IN EUROPE SUMMIT 2021

On day 2 a total of 64 participants where the focus of the sessions lay on tools and mechanisms for evidence-based policymaking.

FIGURE 44: SESSION BANNERS FOR TOOLS AND MECHANISMS FOCUSED DAY 2 OF THE EVIDENCE BASED POLICY IN EUROPE SUMMIT 2021

5.2.2.2 EGI2021

In Year 2, Policy Cloud joined efforts in the Data Driven Policy Cluster to organise the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit 2021. At the EGI2021 conference the cluster organised a joint session at EGI2021 titled “Initiatives for better evidence-based policies in the public sector” on 20 November 2021. The session aimed to raise awareness on the cluster commonalities and start the discussion with EGI and EOSC audiences on its added value for EOSC.

EGI had 543 registrants of which 69 fell in the categories CEO/Manager/Director/Policy Maker.

FIGURE 45: OVERVIEW OF EGI 2021 SESSION SPEAKERS, FROM THE CLUSTER AND EOSC

5.2.3 Next steps

In year 3 the post-event report will be published of the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit and related 3 policy briefs. These insights and reusable materials will be widely disseminated.

Year 3 will see the final Policy Cloud event, where all results will be showcased to potential end-users and the wider stakeholder ecosystem, leveraging on the solid Policy Cloud and Cluster communities established in the first two years.

5.3 Policy Cloud webinars

Webinars are an effective and efficient mechanism to reach a large and geographically spread audience, addressing single topics or results from the project. In the Policy Cloud project webinars will serve two ends:

- Raising awareness: increase the visibility of the work and results of Policy Cloud
- Training: capacity building for end-users, to facilitate adoption

In addition to the objectives mentioned above, the project will also work on building synergies with other H2020 projects and e-governance initiatives.

5.3.1 Webinars Year 1

In its first year, Policy Cloud delivered two webinars, by building synergies with other H2020 projects, namely:

- One webinar in the series of BigDataPilotDemoDays, a series of 9 webinars with BigDataStack, I-BiDaaS and Track&Know during the BDV PPP Summit 2020. Highlighting the adoption and enhancement of two exploitable assets developed under the BigDataStack project. Illustrating the added value for potential adopters through the presentation of the “Policies against Radicalisation” Policy Cloud Pilot³¹. The series was attended by over 400 attendees.
- One webinar was co-organised with DUET and URBANITE projects, during the EBDVF2020 conference. The three projects discussed the “Smart government: co-creating services with the use of AI and Data.”³²

5.3.2 Webinars Year 2

In its second year, Policy Cloud organised and co-organised 6 awareness raising webinars:

Webinar title	Synergies	Date	Impact	Links
The Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking: Impact and Practical Implementations	CyberWatching, DUET, URBANITE	17 February 2021	200 registrants 120+ attendees A joint post event report with practical recommendations for policymakers on the Data Governance Act and Data-Driven Policymaking the report has been downloaded 90+ and viewed 100+ times.	Announcement: https://www.PolicyCloud.eu/news-events/events/data-governance-act-and-data-driven-policymaking-impact-and-practical Post event report: https://PolicyCloud.eu/news-events/news/report-published-data-governance-act
Data Driven Policymaking Week	DEMETER, and ICB members from: CollectiveUP &	26-29 April 2021	200+ registrants 99 attendees Post-event report with practical	Announcement: https://PolicyCloud.eu/news-events/news/data-

³¹ Policy Cloud, Policies against radicalisation webinar insights, <https://policycloud.eu/news-events/news/policies-against-radicalisation-webinar-insights>, retrieved 2020-12-21

³² Policy Cloud, Application track 5 smart society parallel session smart government Slides. <https://policycloud.eu/publications/publications/application-track-5-smart-society-parallel-session-smart-government-co> and recordings: <https://youtu.be/qKFCljs1bCk>, retrieved 2020-12-21

Webinar title	Synergies	Date	Impact	Links
	European Digital Development Alliance, TNO, Lisbon Council for Economic Competitiveness & Social Renewal		recommendations for policymakers on Data Driven Policymaking the report has been published on ZENODO and the website, downloaded 90+ and viewed 100+ times	driven-policymaking-week Post event report: https://PolicyCloud.eu/news-events/news/report-published-data-driven-policymaking-week

TABLE 9: WEBINAR OVERVIEW YEAR 2

5.3.3 Next steps

In the third year Policy Cloud will focus on fostering the take-up of the Policy Cloud tools, webinars will be a great way to provide virtual demonstrations to potential end-users.

In addition, and as mentioned in D7.7 Standardisation Plan and Activities, Policy Cloud will be looking at a joint webinar with StandICT.eu on the planned white paper for standards in “Big Data for Smart Cities”.

5.4 Pilot Co-creation workshops

As part of the co-creation methodology, and under WP6, each pilot will organise a set of four workshops over the course of the project. These workshops will engage policy makers and potential end-users in the co-creation of the Policy Cloud and will provide opportunities for the project to onboard potential end-users on national level.

5.4.1 Co-creation activities Year 1

In addition to the tailored branding and communication material (see section 4), WP7 supports WP6 and the pilots to leverage on the co-creation workshops to raise awareness on Policy Cloud and its added value for the pilots and potential end-users. WP7 supports the pilots in the promotion of the workshops and the outcomes and outputs, prior, during and after the workshop. An event checklist and a set of guidelines for reporting and blogging was developed and made available on the project repository to support the pilots in the promotion around the workshop.

A pilot workshop checklist was created by Trust-IT and provided to each of the pilots, allowing them to request the different communications support activities needed for their individual workshop, allowing WP7 to tailor support to the individual requirements of each pilot. For example, not all workshops can be recorded as the objective is to have optimal co-creation input from policymakers, and recording meetings can lead to hesitancy in sharing ideas. It is up to the individual pilot to gauge whether recording the meeting will be of benefit or not.

FIGURE 46: PROMOTIONAL IMAGE OF POST-CO-CREATION WORKSHOP REPORT

5.4.2 Co-creation activities Year 2

Year 2 saw the first pilot workshop for the intelligent policies for the food value chain pilot, held online 23/02/2021. The workshop focused on how big data and artificial intelligence have been applied to the wine sector, and how Policy Cloud could be applied by both policy makers and private actors to give them effective data-based tools to understand consumer demands, wine trends, consumer opinions, as well as the level and quality of production. WP7 supported WP6 by making the event visible on the Policy Cloud website and attending WP6 meetings to provide strategic advice for the pilot workshops.

5.4.3 Future steps

In M24 (December 2021) pilot workshops are being held for all four pilots. Considering the situation with the global pandemic some of these workshops will be hybrid events and others fully online. Year 3 will see the final round of pilot workshops. All workshops will be supported by WP7, in order to create post event reports as well as stakeholder interviews.

5.5 Podcasts

In M6 Policy Cloud WP7 started a podcast series as a new way of engaging with the Policy Cloud Community, especially considering the Pandemic situation and impossibility of holding in person events. The podcasts provide in depth interviews but in an informal and easy to listen to style.

5.5.1 Podcasts Year 1

In Year 1 two podcasts were published, both covering Policy Cloud pilots. They were also distributed to other popular platforms such as Spotify and iTunes.

The very first podcast showcased the Policies Against Radicalization pilot, featuring partners LeanXcale and Maggioli. The conversation explored the policy support and technical work of the pilot. In Year 1 it was listened to 71 times. The second podcast featured the Crowdsourced Urban Environment Monitoring pilot and was listened to 53 times.

FIGURE 47: POLICY CLOUD PODCAST ON POLICIES AGAINST RADICALISATION PILOT

5.5.2 Podcasts Year 2

A series of four podcasts was recorded over the first two years of the Policy Cloud project, each podcast highlighting one of the four pilot use cases.

FIGURE 48: THE FOUR PODCAST EPISODES ON THE PODCAST HOSTING PLATFORM ANCHOR.FM

These podcasts were hosted by a member of the communications team from Trust-IT Services interacting with a member of the pilot organisations to highlight the importance of the Policy Cloud platform for that specific area of policy.

When each podcast was published, it was accompanied by a news piece, a home page slider, and social media posts including excerpts of the conversation.

So far there have been a total of 270 listens.

FIGURE 49: SLIDER ON THE HOMEPAGE OF THE WEBSITE PROMOTING THE PODCAST

5.5.3 Next steps

From M25, a pay-per-click campaign will be introduced to increase the number of listeners, as the podcasts give great overviews of how the Policy Cloud platform will be beneficial to policymakers and even to industry.

An additional podcast series with ICB members will be considered, to set Policy Cloud in the wider context of data driven policymaking.

5.6 Third Party Events

Policy Cloud aims to engage stakeholders at ICT, Policy and EOSC related third party events. Events are good way to raise awareness on the Policy Cloud results and added value for potential adopters. The consortium will engage stakeholder at third part events through presentations, posters and dissemination material. The KPI set in the GA is the attendance of 30 third party events. Due to the pandemic COVID-19, events attendance has been limited to online formats, at the next iteration of this deliverable the consortium will reassess this KPI and its feasibility.

5.6.1 Third Party Events Year 1

Up to December 2020 (M12) six third party events were attended in a virtual way, and digital material was disseminated.

Event	Date	Action	Stakeholder targeted	Output
EOSC-hub week 2020	18-20 May 2020	Poster presentation	450 p, from EOSC eco-system (R&I, Policy Makers and Industry)	Poster
AIAI 2020	5-7 June 2020	Paper presentation & presentation	AI community	Paper publication
BDV PPP Summit 2020	2 July 2020	Webinar in Joint series #BigDataPilotDemoDays with BigDataStack, I-BiDaaS and Track&Know	BDV PPP projects, Industry, Research & Academia	News item, webinar recordings and slides published
EGI2020	3 November 2020	Presentation and showcasing one of the Policy Cloud videos	Industry and Research & Academia	Recordings and slides published
EBDVF2020	5 November 2020	Joint session with DUET and URBANITE and an exhibition booth	Industry, Policy Makers and Research & Academia	Recordings and slides published
Realising the EOSC. Towards a FAIR research Data Landscape.	16-19 November	Exposition booth	EOSC and Research & Academia	Views of videos and digital flyers and factsheets.

TABLE 10: OVERVIEW OF THIRD-PARTY EVENTS ATTENDED BY POLICY CLOUD AT M12

5.6.2 Third Party Events Year 2

In the second year of the project, Policy Cloud has been presented at 8 third party events.

Event	Date	Action	Stakeholder targeted	Output
12th International Conference on Information and Communication Systems (ICICS 2021)	24-26 May 2021	Paper presentation	Research & Academia	Paper publication
31st Medical Informatics Europe Conference (MIE 2021)	29-31 May 2021	Paper presentation	Research & Academia	Paper publication
17th International Conference on Artificial Intelligence Applications and Innovations (AIAI 2021)	25-27 June 2021	Paper presentation	Research & Academia	Paper publication
MCE2021	13 October 2021	Plenary presentation, Policy Cloud innovation workshop and exposition booth.	Major Cities in Europe CEOs and decision makers (potential end-users)	Promotional video Policy Cloud Pilot in Sofia, slides & recordings published
EGI2021	19 November 2021	Joint session with the Data Driven Policy Cluster Policy Cloud poster presentation	Industry and Research & Academia	Poster, recordings and slides published
Presentación del asistente inteligente de Open Data (Gobierno de Aragón) Workshop	26-29 November 2021	Presentation of Policy Cloud to the Aragon Government	Polymakers	Slides will be made available
EBDVF2021	3 December 2021	Joint session with the Data Driven Policy Cluster	Industry, Policy Makers and	Recordings and slides published

Event	Date	Action	Stakeholder targeted	Output
			Research & Academia	
2021 IEEE International Conference on Progress in Informatics and Computing (PIC-2021)	17-19 December 2021	Paper presentation	Research & Academia	Presentation performed, awaiting paper publication

TABLE 11: OVERVIEW OF THIRD-PARTY EVENTS ATTENDED BY POLICY CLOUD AT M24

5.6.3 Next steps

In the third year, Policy Cloud partners will continue to attend third party events to promote project results with its stakeholder for wider uptake. In addition to the scientific and technology focused conferences, and in line with the review comments made in May 2021, the consortium will seek to share its knowledge and present its results with the policymaking audience in third party events.

6 Measuring impact and monitoring activities

6.1 KPIs

The Communication Strategy for Policy Cloud defines and monitors **regular activities throughout the 36 months** ensuring continuous content production (web, social media), outreach and stakeholder engagement based on the Specific Measurable Achievable Relevant Time phased (SMART) approach. The set of KPIs defined in the table below, will help the consortium work towards the envisioned impact, the status at M24 (December 2021), at the writing of this deliverable, as well as the planning for M25-M36, has been measured and added.

Number	Concept	Description	M12	M24	Planning M25-M36
7.1	Community Database	<p>Policy Cloud profiled community of 1000 from at least 20 EU countries by M12, over 1,500 by M24 & up to 2,000 by month 36. With a focus on engagement via LinkedIn.</p> <p><i>Note this KPI has been updated from the GA.</i></p>	<p>Database currently holds 260+ connections, LinkedIn community has 437 connections, from 7 countries, Twitter has 133 followers</p> <p>Mounting to a total of over 800 connections</p>	<p>Database currently holds 260+ connections, LinkedIn community has 1.800+ connections, Twitter has 322 followers</p> <p>Mounting to a total of over 2.122 connections</p>	<p>Gain followers via LinkedIn for a direct communication and build an addition stakeholder database to scout valuable project connections to connect to for dissemination, event attendance and social media community.</p>
7.2	Social Media Coverage targets	<p>500 Tweets >500 non-affiliated Twitter followers</p> <p>800 connections on LinkedIn</p> <p>by M36</p>	<p>✔ KPI achieved for M12 with:</p> <p>Twitter: 210 tweets, 133 followers</p>	<p>✔ KPI achieved for M24 with:</p> <p>Twitter: 271 tweets, 322 followers</p> <p>LinkedIn: 1803 followers</p>	<p>Additional 200 social media posts</p> <p>Link to additional 500+ connections on</p>

Number	Concept	Description	M12	M24	Planning M25-M36
			LinkedIn: 437 followers		twitter and LinkedIn
7.3	Website targets	<p>Policy Cloud mentioned in at least 30 external social media channels by M36</p> <p>For the website, it will measure the number of unique visits to main services, downloads of outputs, and site bounce rates.</p>	<p>✔ KPI achieved for M12 with:</p> <p>9 backlinks</p> <p>4 referring domains</p> <p>21 twitter mentions</p>	<p>✔ KPI achieved for M24 with:</p> <p>9 backlinks</p> <p>4 referring domains</p> <p>31 twitter mentions</p>	Additional 20+ backlinks and referring domains.
7.4	Event related targets	For the 2 end-user workshops a minimum of >40 participants expected to attend that range from policy stakeholders, researchers, industrial players, stakeholders working in the public administrations	Not yet applicable	<p>✔ KPI achieved for M24 with:</p> <p>Year 1 end-user event: 220+ registrants, 120+ attendees</p>	Final event to be organised in Year 3

Number	Concept	Description	M12	M24	Planning M25-M36
7.5	Video production targets	4 Generic videos over the 36 months – the first that may be carried out in the first reporting period, on the overall objectives & principal assets of Policy Cloud with a duration of 40 seconds, then one video (with 1-minute duration) on each of the pilot cases developed (once we have information on this) and the impact achieved of assets introduced as part of the EOSC service catalogue. Over 200 individual views to the videos upload onto YouTube channel	KPI achieved for M24 with: 6 promotional Videos, published on the Policy Cloud YouTube channel 12 webinar recordings and 2 playlists available on the Policy Cloud YouTube channel, the other on the BDVA YouTube channel. Views on YouTube: 5800 4 podcasts on Soundcloud and Spotify, Listens:270+	Additional webinar and training recordings	

Number	Concept	Description	M12	M24	Planning M25-M36
7.6	Impact of social networking and viral marketing	# of assets introduced as part of EOSC portal or service catalogue to be continuously monitored, - # of end-users exploiting the pilot use cases - relevant dialogue with policy makers monitored.	Not yet applicable	70 potential end-users from public administrations of major cities in Europe attended the Policy Cloud workshop at the MCE2021 innovation workshop. During the co-creation workshops in WP6 relevant dialogues have been initiated and will be followed up on in year 3.	Policy Cloud assets to be taken up by EOSC Portal in year 3 Follow up on relevant dialogues with policymakers attending the co-creation workshops.

7.7	Impact of media outreach	<p>10 newsletters circulated to subscribed community members by M36.</p> <p>Circa 800 subscribers aligned with the LinkedIn connections is an appropriate benchmark. The newsletters will generate increased traffic on the website, an increased number of stakeholders registered to the community database and to social media channels.</p> <p>12 articles by specialised and/or general media outlets by M36. Trust-IT has a database of approx. 200 individual press & media contacts within the vertical industry sector collected as part of its desktop research used for its work in the Common</p>	<p>1 to be published in M12</p> <p>2 contents published on CORDIS</p>	<p> KPI achieved for M24 with:</p> <p>5 newsletters published at M24</p> <p>8 contents published on CORDIS & EO SC</p> <p>2 specialised blog posts</p> <p>9 scientific articles produced</p>	<p>5 newsletters to be published in year 3</p> <p>Continue to publish in external channels for a wider outreach.</p> <p>In year 3 the consortium will look into pilot articles in local languages.</p>
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Number	Concept	Description	M12	M24	Planning M36	M25-
		<p>Dissemination Booster (CDB).</p> <p>6 content published on external channels:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none">-Space for project results: "CORDIS Results Packs" & "Results in Brief"-Horizon Magazine-Project stories-Researcheu results magazine-Researcheu focus-Newsletters-Euronews Science and Technology-Events on the website of DG Research& Innovation-Events on the website of CORDIS-Openaire - open access scientific publishing <p>by M36</p>				

Number	Concept	Description	M12	M24	Planning M25-M36
7.8	Engagement at workshops, webinars and ICT, Open Access events, EOOSC related events	<p>2 workshops by M36, with 80 attendees at the Policy Cloud workshops by M36</p> <p>At least 30 stakeholders reached through the Policy Cloud webinars by M36</p> <p>Participation at 30 relevant events by M36</p>	<p>✔ KPI achieved for M12 with:</p> <p>6 third part events attended</p> <p>2 Policy Cloud webinars organised, attended by 100+p</p> <p>2 podcasts with a total of 134 listens</p>	<p>✔ KPI achieved for M24with:</p> <p>1 joint workshop/annual event, 220+ registrants and 120+ attendees</p> <p>2 innovation workshops organised</p> <p>Dissemination activities performed at 14 third party events</p> <p>7 Policy Cloud webinars organised</p> <p>4 podcasts with a total of 270 listens</p>	<p>Attend 16 third party events</p> <p>Organise 1 final event</p> <p>Organise at least 2 additional webinars</p> <p>Dedicated PPC campaigns to promote the podcasts to a wider public, and reach total of 500 listens for all podcasts.</p>

TABLE 12: KPI DEFINITION, MONITORING AND ROADMAP FOR M25-36

6.2 Monitoring

An Activity Tracker spreadsheet is used to monitor the monthly progress made on KPIs, giving the possibility to adjust effort according to trends. An Editorial Calendar is also used to plan upcoming news, events, and social media activity. This allows a timely distribution of outputs and communication.

A Policy Cloud Dashboard has been set up to monitor the impact of the communication actions on the social media community and website traffic, via Google analytics. There are regular internal meetings to review website performance.

FIGURE 50: IMPRESSION OF THE POLICY CLOUD MONITORING DASHBOARD

6.3 Communications Timeline

The timeline below shows communication and dissemination activities linked to the Policy Cloud key pillars (see section 2), and planned for the next six months.

FIGURE 51: SAMPLE TIMELINE OF COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES M25-M30

7 Conclusions

The present document is the basis for all Communication and Dissemination activities to be carried out in Policy Cloud over the project's lifetime. The main conclusions are:

- The “Policy Cloud Communication and Dissemination Plan” is tightly linked to the project results and therefore is to be considered as a living document: It will be up to the “Communication, Dissemination and Impact” work package to timely update it whenever necessary.
- WP7 activities in the first twenty-four months of the project have been conducted with good coordination and produced tangible results, including completion of project branding, launch of the new website, visibility at events and production of a number of collaterals.
- All consortium partners have shown good alignment and high commitment in development and implementation of the present plan.

Next steps defined are:

- A timeline for the period January 2022 – June 2022 (M25-M30) has been developed and it will be followed as part of WP7 as well as an overview from M12-M36 for Policy Cloud (see section 1).
- During the sixth consortium meeting new communication material and activities will be presented and discussed with partners for optimal use and outreach.
- In January 2022, WP6 and WP7 will align on additional engagement mechanisms for the national communities of the pilot projects.
- Early 2022 WP7 will team up with the Data Driven Policy Cluster to jointly produce, publish and promote the post-event report of the Evidence Based Policy in Europe Summit, and 3 joint policy briefs.
- In year 3 WP7 will be promoting the Policy Cloud Data Marketplace in tailored promotional campaigns.
- In this third and last year, WP7 will support the pilots in onboarding its local end-user communities, showcasing the added value of the full implementation, tapping into the activated Policy Cloud social media community.

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ANNEX 1 - Policy Cloud Dissemination Channels and Mechanisms

FIGURE 52: POLICY CLOUD COMMUNICATION & DISSEMINATION CHANNELS AND MECHANISMS